

Conservation Police Officer Aquatic Invasive Species Engagement

Elizabeth Golebie¹, Katie O'Reilly^{3,4}, Greg Hitzroth^{3,4}, Brandon Fehrenbacher², Chris Taylor⁴, Greg Spyreas⁴, North Joffe-Nelson¹, & Carena J. van Riper¹

¹ Department of Natural Resources and Environmental Sciences,
University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign

² Illinois Department of Natural Resources

³ Illinois-Indiana Sea Grant

⁴ Illinois Natural History Survey – Prairie Research Institute

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

Conservation police officers enforce laws and provide educational opportunities for interest groups such as boaters, anglers, and aquarium hobbyists that are at risk of spreading aquatic invasive species (AIS). These interactions are not only an effective means of ensuring regulations are followed but are also seen as a way to build trust within the communities that conservation police officers serve while helping retain recreationists and the revenue they generate through conservation fees. However, little is known about how people are currently interpreting their interactions with law enforcement officers, and in turn, how conservation police officers can improve their practices associated with natural resource protection. The aim of this study was therefore to engage multiple interest groups through environmental social science research and AIS outreach workshop focused on expanding AIS prevention efforts. We addressed two research objectives:

Objective 1: Understand how educational content on species identification across taxa (i.e., fish, plants, crayfish) can be enhanced to increase conservation police officer capacity for managing the spread of AIS

- A. How can AIS training of conservation police officers across the state of Illinois be improved?
- B. What is the impact of training workshops in increasing AIS identification and enforcement among conservation police officers?

Objective 2: Examine the educational needs and interpretation of AIS enforcement according to boaters, anglers, and aquarium hobbyists across the state of Illinois

- A. What are the experiences of Illinois boaters, anglers, and aquarium hobbyists with AIS regulations and conservation police officers?
- B. How do people's thoughts and feelings influence their intentions to comply with AIS regulations?

Key Findings and Management Implications

Objective 1: Understand how educational content on species identification across taxa (i.e., fish, plants, crayfish) can be enhanced to increase conservation police officer capacity for managing the spread of AIS

Summary of AIS educational workshop

- A three-hour AIS workshop was offered at the 2024 Illinois Conservation Police Officer annual training. A total of 102 (out of 143) officers attended.
- Content areas included the causes and consequences of AIS spread, relevant laws and enforcement options, outreach resources, and identification of invasive fishes, crayfishes, and plants.
- Breakout sessions provided officers with hands-on experience identifying species. Officers had the opportunity to practice by handling live and preserved specimens.
- Officers were provided with printed and electronic resources including an AIS identification card, a suite of documents outlining laws and enforcement options for each species covered in the workshop, and cards with phrases related to AIS enforcement translated to Spanish and Mandarin.

Officer needs assessment from pre- and post-workshop surveys

- Pre- and post-workshop surveys were conducted to enhance our preparations and determine workshop impact. Our research process engaged 84 conservation police officers (response rate = 56%) in a pre-workshop survey and 82 (response rate = 85%) in a post-workshop survey.
- Nearly all officers who participated in each survey indicated that they typically encountered AIS at least a few times each year.
- In the pre-workshop survey, proposed workshop topics and resources were evaluated and generally deemed “moderately” useful.
 - Officers indicated that lists of expert contacts would be most useful and requested recommendations for online resources and digital versions of any printed resources.
 - Commonly described challenges to AIS enforcement included species identification, lack of knowledge among the public, and lack of prosecution.
- In the post-workshop survey, the usefulness of all presented topics and training methods (i.e., presentations, hands-on identification, take-home resources) were evaluated as “moderately” to “extremely useful.”

- The hands-on opportunity to work with live specimens was noted as particularly useful. The crayfish identification workshop, handouts, and the break-out session structure received the most positive feedback.
- Suggestions for future workshops included more live specimens, more handling time, a broader set of species, and inclusion of native species for comparison.
- Workshop learning
 - Officers reported higher confidence in AIS education after the workshop, as compared with confidence levels reported in the pre-workshop survey
 - Officers reported high levels of knowledge recall, skill development, workshop engagement, and application of what was learned to a broader context.

Implications and best practices for future workshops

- Workshops can increase officer capacity for enforcing AIS species regulations and educating the public about these issues, thus minimizing the risk of costly invasions. Recommendations for future workshops include:
 - Prioritize hands-on activities and opportunities to handle live specimens; these activities are most likely to enhance workshop engagement and learning.
 - Focus on species that officers are most likely to encounter in the field, rather than those that are interesting or have “shock value.”
 - Develop high quality take-home materials to help officers to recall pertinent knowledge and have access to contact information if questions arise.
 - Account for logistics in the workshop development process, including funding, legal approval, site coordination, and agency buy-in.
 - Align future training sessions with required annual meetings to ensure widespread participation.
- Inclusion of an advisory board in this project was fundamentally important. Counsel was provided throughout the research process from experts that studied various AIS taxa and the Illinois Department of Natural Resources (IDNR) conservation police. These same individuals were therefore well poised to deliver the workshop content because they were involved in workshop development. This research approach serves as a model for future research.
 - Law enforcement partners provided useful background information on AIS law enforcement, relevant challenges and needs of conservation police officers, and feasible pathways for expanding AIS prevention efforts.

- Biologists selected relevant species for the workshop, developed educational material, and delivered instruction on species identification.
- Social scientists coordinated the project, identified the needs of multiple interest groups spanning conservation police officers, boaters, anglers, and aquarium hobbyists, and evaluated workshop efficacy.
- Educational workshops offer indirect and long-term benefits that are challenging to evaluate in definitive terms. A pre-post survey design is essential for generating empirical results and drawing conclusions about the impact of research.
 - Tradeoffs were made in the decision to collect survey data via phone at the end of the workshop versus using hard copies of a questionnaire or more in-depth qualitative methods. Though logistically simpler, responses to open-ended responses were brief.
 - Following up to assess enforcement outcomes (e.g., citations and warnings issued, number of inspections) and longer-term reflections from workshop participants will provide a more complete understanding of workshop efficacy.

Objective 2: Examine the educational needs and interpretation of AIS enforcement according to boaters, anglers, and aquarium hobbyists across the state of Illinois

Summary of Illinois boaters, anglers, and aquarium hobbyists' experiences

- A public needs assessment was performed in 2023 to complement the conservation police officer workshop and surveys. This process engaged 783 Illinois residents who had gone fishing (68%), boating (65%), or owned a home aquarium (41%) in the past three years to understand how they interpreted their interactions with conservation police officers.
 - Anglers reported an average of 16 years of experience. Approximately half of respondents fished primarily from shorelines. Nearly all used live bait at least occasionally.
 - Boaters reported an average of 12 years of experience. A majority of respondents (59%) borrowed, rather than owned, the watercraft they used.
 - Hobbyists reported an average of 7 years of experience, and commonly obtained their species from chain stores and local fish stores.
- Across all interest groups, 75% were White, 60% were female, and the average age was 40.
- On average, respondents were somewhat familiar with ecological, social, and legal facets of AIS, and felt AIS were moderately relevant to their own lives.

- Approximately half of respondents had previously interacted with a conservation police officer.
- Respondents reported high levels of trust in conservation police officers, with just over half indicating they had high or very high levels of trust. There was no significant relationship between number of past experiences with conservation police officers and general level of trust (Pearson's correlation = 0.04, $p = 0.32$).

Summary of factors related to intentions to comply with AIS regulations

- Trustworthiness and trust: Conservation police officers were seen as trustworthy in the public eye. Respondents believed they had strong ability, benevolence, and integrity to equal degrees.
 - The more recreationists perceived conservation police officers as trustworthy, the more likely they were to trust in their decisions and values.
- Emotions: Respondents expressed positive emotions towards conservation police officers. On average, respondents agreed that they feel hopeful when thinking about conservation police officers and disagreed that they feel fearful
 - Emotions were rooted in trust; trust in conservation police officers was associated with more hope and less fear.
- Risk perceptions: Respondents slightly agreed that their local environment was susceptible to AIS and expected that impacts to themselves and their community would be moderate.
 - Perceived risks were higher when emotional responses to conservation police officers (both hope and fear) were higher.
- Behavior: We measured intentions to comply with laws related to AIS during fishing, boating, and aquarium hobby activities. The likelihood of engaging in preventative behaviors was moderate across all behaviors considered.
 - Boating and angling behaviors were positively influenced by risk perceptions. The more susceptible recreationists felt to species invasions, and the more severe they perceive potential impacts to be, the more likely they were to comply with AIS laws.
 - The more recreationists felt hopeful about conservation police officer interactions, the more they intended to comply with AIS laws.
 - Boating behaviors were negatively influenced by fear of conservation police officers. The more that boaters indicated they felt fearful of conservation police officers, the less likely they were to comply with laws designed to minimize species invasions via boats.

Management implications

- Emotions are an important trigger for behavioral responses to enforcement of AIS in Illinois. Though emotional responses are shaped by many factors over time, attention should be directed to fostering positive relationships between recreationists and conservation police officers.
- Trust is instrumental in shaping the beliefs and emotions of recreationists and can be built through responsiveness to public questions and consistency in enforcement.
- Training programs like the one implemented through this research can help to strengthen the trustworthiness of conservation police officers, which is a precondition for building trust.
- Individuals can be motivated to care about AIS by drawing connections to other issues or activities they care about. For instance, providing an example of how AIS threaten sportfishing opportunities is likely to result in greater concern about AIS among anglers, and ultimately greater compliance with relevant laws.

Overall Conclusions

- Scientists, law enforcement agencies, and public interest groups like boaters, anglers, and aquarium hobbyists each play a role in preventing the spread of AIS. Each group warrants managerial attention, and if integrated in research, will offer a more complete set of options for expanding AIS prevention in the future.
- Future research should seek to ask integrated questions that require input from each of these groups. Below are example questions for future research that can build on the present study.
 - Which species are most invasive (or likely to become invasive) and need to be prioritized by law enforcement?
 - How can AIS identification be improved to enhance enforcement?
 - Why do people spread AIS and react in different ways to authority figures in science and management?
 - What makes people most likely to follow regulations?
 - How should agencies communicate with different audiences and which groups should be prioritized?
 - Which other agencies would benefit from similar trainings and how can inter-agency communication and coordination be improved?

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For additional information, please contact:

Carena J. van Riper, PhD
Department of Natural Resources and Environmental Sciences
University of Illinois Urbana-Champaign
1102 S Goodwin Ave, Urbana, IL 61801
Phone: 217-244-9317
Email: cvanripe@illinois.edu

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BACKGROUND

Numerous aquatic invasive species (AIS) may be introduced to Illinois waterways from boaters, anglers, and aquarium hobbyists. Illinois conservation police officers are instrumental in mitigating the risk of introduction by enforcing laws related to AIS and providing educational information when interacting with the public. To expand AIS prevention efforts, there was an expressed need for AIS outreach workshops to enhance the training of conservation police officers in species identification and generate public knowledge of AIS law enforcement. Therefore, **we sought to enhance educational outreach and law enforcement related to AIS prevention in Illinois** through a two-pronged research approach from 2023-2025. The first facet of this project involved implementing and evaluating **a workshop for Illinois conservation police officers** to provide content on species identification across multiple taxa including fish, plants, and crayfish. In the second facet of the project, we sought to **understand public needs** related to education and enforcement of AIS. An advisory board was formed to guide the two facets of this project, and in turn, increase conservation police officer capacity for managing the spread of AIS across the state of Illinois.

OFFICER NEEDS ASSESSMENTS AND WORKSHOP

An AIS outreach workshop was delivered during the annual in-service training for all Illinois conservation police officers in February 2024. We used a longitudinal research approach to inform workshop development and evaluate workshop efficacy. Prior to the workshop, a needs assessment was conducted, and after the workshop, a post-workshop survey was conducted. The needs assessments, workshop, and post-workshop survey are presented sequentially in this section.

Methods for the Officer Needs Assessment

The needs assessment was conducted in February 2024, approximately three weeks before the workshop. A link to a Qualtrics survey was sent to an email list of active conservation police officers (n=145) across the state of Illinois. A total of 90 officers opened the survey link, and 84 opted to participate (response rate = 58%). The questionnaire is presented in Appendix A.

Results from Officer Needs Assessment

Respondent characteristics

Officers who participated in the pre-workshop survey reported an average of 9.86 years of experience ($SD = 7.80$) and represented all five management zones in the Illinois Department of Natural Resources (IDNR) (see Table 1). Approximately half of all officers who participated indicated that they encountered AIS a few times a year (52%).

Table 1.

Profile of Illinois Department of Natural Resources (IDNR) conservation police officers who participated in the pre-workshop survey

Variables	N (%)
Age [M, SD]	[36.99, 9.40]
Years of experience as a conservation police officer [M, SD]	[9.86, 7.80]
<i>DNR management zone of employment</i>	
Northwest Region 1	18 (21.4)
Northeast Region 2	18 (21.4)
East-Central Region 3	12 (14.3)
West-Central Region 4	12 (14.3)
South Region 5	24 (28.6)
Frequency of encountering invasive species while working	
Never	1 (1.2)
Once a year or less	10 (11.9)
A few times a year	44 (52.4)
Around once a month	13 (15.5)
At least once a week	16 (19.0)

Training needs

First, officers were asked to comment on any challenges they had faced when enforcing AIS laws or engaging with the public on these issues. A total of 51 officers (61%) commented on these challenges. A summary of responses and a selection of representative comments are below.

- The most common response ($n = 14$) was that **species identification is a key challenge** for enforcement. Some officers commented that it can be difficult to

immediately identify a species while on patrol, and others shared the difficulty in ensuring the species is indeed invasive.

- Eleven officers spoke to the **lack of knowledge among the general public** when it comes to AIS and the related regulations. Officers had also observed low levels of concern about the threats AIS pose.
 - “The general public does not know anything about invasive species. Example: As a CPO, I will check a fisherman with a bucket filled with live goby's and they have no idea what they have.”
- Seven officers described **issues specific to fishing bait**, including the difficulty in determining where an invasive bait species was obtained, the failure of bait shops to follow regulations, and challenges caused by bait being sold across state lines.
 - “People often will use alive rusty crayfish when fishing on the IL River. Whether a bait shop around here is selling them or it is in a Chicago area it is unclear. I run into it all the time in the summer because people buy them from a bait shop and think it should be okay.”
 - “Certain species are allowed and sold in other states. Some sport fishermen buy these species and transport them to IL to be used for fishing. ex. you can buy rusty crayfish in Indiana and use them on Lake Michigan, but you can't buy them here and use them on Lake Michigan. Also, Goby can be caught everyday in Cook Co and most fishermen use them as bait. These fishermen harvest them from Lake Michigan and then use them immediately on Lake Michigan.”
- Five officers indicated that they have experienced a **lack of prosecution** of AIS violations, including case dismissals.
 - “Court system not taking it seriously and not holding the guilty party accountable”
 - “The lack of knowledge amongst prosecutors, agency leaders, and officers on the importance of AIS enforcement. Identifying and getting adequate prosecution for Internet crimes and those who operate outside of the US but ship to the US.”
- Many **AIS are already established in Illinois waterways**. Five officers spoke to the challenges of dealing with AIS that are already present in the ecosystem.
 - “Their presence in the waterways already can be a defense for the person having them in possession”
 - “They are so prevalent in some areas (round goby) it is not widely understood they are invasive.”

- “I find it difficult to write an inadvertent violator a Class A misdemeanor and mandatory court appearance in an area where the invasive species already exists.”
- The **complexity of enforcement** and the need for training has also posed a challenge for some officers (n = 5)
 - “Not having a clear cut answer for enforcement action. I know its not a one size fits all but if we had a blueprint or contact to walk us through all the violations it would be greatly appreciated.”
 - “Determining the correct statutes to write on ticket. Advice on enforcement action and what to do with seized species when encountered.”
 - “Illinois changed the Illinois commercial fishing and aquatic life dealer statutes along with the commercial fishing ad rule several years ago and no training was provided to explain these laws.”
- Additional relevant but uncommon comments are below:
 - “Language barriers”
 - “The requirement to empty live wells before returning to a residence. Fishermen want to keep fish alive to go weigh in, or until they home to clean them. Fish get very soft and slimy after they die.”
 - “None other than getting covered in slim and wacked while working the rivers and streams from the abundance of Copi (Asian Carp)”

Next, officers evaluated the usefulness of a suite of potential training topics related to AIS (see Table 2). Perceived usefulness ranged from ‘somewhat’ to ‘moderately’ useful, with invasive fish identification highlighted as a particularly useful training topic ($M = 4.37, SD = 0.80$).

Table 2.

Conservation police officers’ perceived usefulness of proposed training topics related to AIS

Usefulness of AIS training topics¹	M (SD)
Reviewing the causes and effects of invasive species spread	3.52 (1.08)
Identifying invasive crayfish species	4.08 (1.06)
Identifying invasive plant species	3.77 (1.29)
Identifying invasive fish species	4.37 (0.80)
Enforcing invasive species laws related to boating and angling	4.20 (0.93)
Enforcing invasive species laws related to aquariums	3.11 (1.30)

¹Measured on a 5-point Likert scale from 1 (not at all useful) to 5 (extremely useful)

Officers were invited to share any additional topics related to AIS identification and enforcement that would be helpful to know. A total of 20 officers left comments. Nine officers requested information pertaining to identification, including **tips for efficiently identifying species and resources such as picture cards and websites**. Six officers requested information pertaining to enforcement, including **legal requirements, specific enforcement actions, and evidence handling procedures**. An additional five officers requested information about **AIS impacts and management**, such as the effect of invasive carp on sportfish, steps that can be taken to minimize spread, and management actions that are currently in practice.

Officers were asked to report their level of confidence in providing education related to AIS (see Table 3). On average, officers reported being slightly to somewhat confident ($M = 2.72$, $SD = 0.97$).

Table 3.

Levels of confidence in providing education and instructions related to AIS

	M (SD)
Confidence¹ ($\alpha=.867$, $\Omega=.879$, $AVE=.714$)	2.72 (0.97)
Educating others about how to identify invasive species	2.68 (1.01)
Providing instructions to industry about how to follow laws pertaining to invasive species	2.51 (1.15)
Providing instructions to the general public about how to follow laws pertaining to invasive species	2.98 (1.13)

¹Measured on a Likert scale ranging from 1 (not at all confident) to 5 (Extremely confident)

Resources for AIS information

We asked officers how often they used different information sources for their own reference while working, as well as how often they recommended a variety of sources to the public (see Table 4). The extent to which officers used resources was generally low, in that no given resource was used often or very often. The most common resources that officers relied on included other conservation police officers ($M = 3.04$, $SD = 1.08$) and online resources ($M = 3.02$, $SD = 1.07$). Officers sometimes referred members of the public to biologists ($M = 3.01$, $SD = 1.28$) and online resources ($M = 2.90$, $SD = 1.20$).

Table 4.*Sources consulted for information about AIS*

Information Sources¹	M (SD)
<i>Sources used while working</i>	
Other conservation police officers	3.04 (1.08)
Biologists	2.67 (1.11)
Online resources	3.02 (1.07)
Species identification cards	2.12 (1.08)
Brochures, fact sheets, or other printed material	2.10 (1.04)
Other ²	
<i>Sources recommended to members of the public</i>	
Other conservation police officers	2.18 (0.93)
Biologists	3.01 (1.28)
Online resources	2.90 (1.20)
Species identification cards	1.95 (1.04)
Brochures, fact sheets, or other printed material	2.28 (1.25)
Other ³	

¹Measured on a Likert scale where 1 = “Never” and 5 = “Very often”

²Six individuals indicated they sometimes, often, or very often use *other resources*. They listed ‘laws’ (n = 1), phone apps (n = 1), and ‘officers/investigators in other agencies who focus on AIS enforcement’ (n = 1) or declined to explain further (n = 3).

³Four individuals indicated they ‘sometimes’ recommend *other resources* but declined to explain further.

We considered developing several resources for distribution at the AIS outreach workshop, including laminated fact sheets, species identification cards, and lists of expert contacts who could be consulted. Officers were asked how useful these resources would be (see Table 5). Officers indicated that all three proposed resources would be ‘moderately’ to ‘extremely’ helpful, with lists of expert contacts being the most useful ($M = 4.39$, $SD = 0.92$).

Table 5.*Helpfulness of resources that could be provided during the workshop*

Helpfulness of resources¹	M (SD)
Laminated fact sheets	3.99 (1.14)
Species identification cards	4.07 (1.15)
Lists of expert contacts who would be consulted	4.39 (0.92)

¹Measured on a 5-point Likert scale from 1 (not at all helpful) to 5 (extremely helpful)

Officers had the opportunity to **list any other resources that would be helpful for species identification**. A total of 14 officers provided input. Responses are summarized below, alongside representative comments.

- Five officers requested **websites or other online resources**, such as phone apps
 - “List of websites I could go to and get an accurate representation of what the invasive species looks like.”
- Three officers requested **digital versions** of any printed resources
 - “Physical species identification cards to keep with us and a PDF version to have saved on our work phones.”
- Two officers emphasized the importance of lists of expert contacts
 - “a list of contacts to help us in the field would be greatly appreciated.”
- Three officers shared **suggestions for how information could be disseminated to the public**, including information in the fishing digest, better public access to information on laws, and presentations at public events.
 - “Establish a presentation that could be presented at earth days or science nights at schools or public events so CPOs could hand out information. Build new educational trailers that have a section about invasive species along with educational materials and trinkets to hand out.”

Additional comments

Officers had the opportunity to provide additional thoughts at the end of the questionnaire. Seven individuals replied, primarily offering **additional suggestions for the workshop**. These suggestions included: 1) focusing on the species that pose the largest threats; 2) providing information, knowledge, and resources that can be used in the field; 3) offering an annual education refresher on ID, enforcement, and contacts; and 4) strategies for educating the public on the importance of AIS.

Officer Workshop

Our AIS workshop was conducted at the Illinois conservation police officer annual training, on February 27th, 2024. A total of 102 officers were in attendance, representing 71% of those who were invited to attend (n = 143), and 63% of those currently employed (n = 162). The workshop lasted three hours and covered several content areas (see Figure 1). Upon arriving at the conference center, officers were provided with a folder containing a variety of resources that can be used in the field to support AIS identification and enforcement. These resources included an AIS identification card (see Appendix B), suite of documents outlining laws and enforcement options for each species that would be covered in the workshop, and translation cards that had been developed by the Loyola Language Lab for prior AIS workshops. Based on feedback collected during the officer needs assessment, we also made digital versions of each of these resources available to the officers.

Figure 1.

Schedule of presentations and activities during the AIS workshop offered to Illinois conservation police officers

AIS Workshop Schedule

12:15-12:30	Welcome & Overview Dr. Carena van Riper & Dr. Elizabeth Golebie, University of Illinois CPO Brandon Fehrenbacher <i>Main room</i>		
	Group 1	Group 2	Group 3
12:35-1:05	Invasive plants Dr. Greg Spyreas <i>Main room</i> 		
1:10-1:40	Invasive fish Dr. Katie O'Reilly <i>Fountain Hall</i> 		
1:45-2:15	Invasive crayfish Dr. Chris Taylor <i>Kirkland Hall</i> 		
2:20-2:40	AIS law enforcement CPO Brandon Fehrenbacher <i>Main room</i>		
2:40-2:45	AIS outreach and action Greg Hitzroth, Illinois Indiana Sea Grant <i>Main room</i>		
2:45	Conclusion & survey Dr. Elizabeth Golebie, University of Illinois <i>Main room</i>		

We began the workshop by welcoming officers, introducing the individuals who would be delivering instruction throughout the day, and providing a series of introductory remarks (see Figure 2). First, we presented a case study to illustrate the costs and challenges associated with AIS control. Second, we provided a review of the enforcement actions that officers can take to minimize the spread of AIS. The goal of these presentations was to emphasize the importance of AIS prevention and inspire officers to increase their capacity to conduct AIS related enforcement.

Figure 2.

Conservation police officers in attendance at the AIS workshop introductory presentation

After the introductory presentations, officers were divided into three groups of approximately 35 officers each to move through three breakout sessions on plant, fish, and crayfish identification. In each breakout session, expert biologists provided instruction on identifying some of the most concerning AIS in Illinois. Plants included Eurasian Water Milfoil (*Myriophyllum spicatum*), Curly-leaf Pondweed (*Potamogeton crispus*), and Flowering Rush (*Butomus umbellatus*). Fish included Northern Snakehead (*Channa argus*), Grass Carp (*Ctenopharyngodon idella*), and Black Carp (*Mylopharyngodon piceus*). Crayfish included Red Swamp Crayfish (*Procambarus clarkii*), Rusty Crayfish (*Faxonius rusticus*), and Marbled Crayfish (*Procambarus virginalis*). After an instructional presentation, officers had the opportunity to practice identifying species by handling live specimens, preserved specimens, and models of each species that was covered (see Figure 3).

Figure 3.

Hands-on identification practice with (A) invasive plants, (B) fish, and (C) crayfish

Following the breakout sessions, the full group of officers came back together for several presentations. Training on enforcing laws related to AIS was provided by presenting several past and ongoing cases and reviewing the most relevant laws and corresponding options for enforcement. Next, officers were given an overview of the outreach programming that Illinois-Indiana Sea Grant and Illinois Natural History Survey conducts, including available resources that officers can share with the public. Finally, we concluded the workshop by thanking everyone for their time and requesting participation in a post-workshop survey.

Methods for Post-Workshop Survey

At the conclusion of the workshop, the 102 officers that were in attendance were invited to participate in a second survey. A QR code was displayed on the projected screens for participants to access the survey on their phones or computers. A survey link was also emailed to officers approximately one week after the workshop ended. A total of 82 officers completed the survey directly following the workshop and 5 completed the survey after receiving the email link (87 total respondents; 85% response rate). The survey questionnaire is available in Appendix C.

Results from Post-Workshop Survey

Respondent characteristics

Officers who participated in the post-workshop survey had an average of 7.16 years of experience ($SD = 1.50$) and represented all five DNR management zones (see Table 6). Similar to the pre-workshop survey, approximately half of respondents indicated that they encountered AIS a few times a year (52%).

Table 6.

Profile of Illinois conservation police officers who participated in the post-workshop survey

Variables	N (%)
Age [M, SD]	[35.27, 8.32]
Years of experience as a conservation police officer [M, SD]	7.16 (1.50)
<i>DNR management zone of employment</i>	
Northwest Region 1	21 (25.9)
Northeast Region 2	25 (30.9)
East-Central Region 3	9 (11.1)
West-Central Region 4	9 (11.1)
South Region 5	17 (21.0)
Frequency of encountering invasive species while working	
Never	3 (3.7)
Once a year or less	9 (11.0)
A few times a year	43 (52.4)
Around once a month	14 (17.1)
At least once a week	13 (15.9)

Workshop usefulness

Officers were invited to rate the level of usefulness of each of the training topics that were provided (see Table 6). The content on crayfish identification was perceived as particularly useful ($M = 4.53$, $SD = 0.70$), but all topics presented were rated as at least moderately useful. Likewise, all three methods—PowerPoint presentations ($M = 4.11$, $SD = 0.84$), hands-on identification ($M = 4.56$, $SD = 0.71$), and take-home resources ($M = 4.32$, $SD = 0.81$)—were rated as moderately to extremely useful.

Table 7.*Conservation police officers' perceived usefulness of the AIS workshop*

	M (SD)
Usefulness of topics¹	
Reviewing the causes and effects of invasive species spread	4.32 (0.80)
Identifying invasive crayfish species	4.53 (0.70)
Identifying invasive plant species	4.01 (0.85)
Identifying invasive fish species	4.37 (0.75)
Enforcing invasive species laws related to boating and angling	4.26 (0.75)
Enforcing invasive species laws related to aquariums	3.94 (1.02)
Usefulness of methods¹	
PowerPoint presentations from invasive species experts	4.11 (0.84)
Hands-on identification exercises with live specimens	4.56 (0.71)
Take-home resources (ID cards, info sheets, etc.) about invasive species identification and enforcement strategies	4.32 (0.81)

¹Measured on a 5-point Likert scale from 1 (not at all useful) to 5 (extremely useful)

Survey respondents were asked to provide input on what was most useful about the workshop. A total of 37 officers chose to provide input. About half of those who commented (n = 18) pointed to the **usefulness of the hands-on opportunity** to work with live specimens and models. Several officers (n = 8) specifically highlighted **crayfish identification** as the most useful component of the workshop. Five officers shared that the **handouts** were the most helpful (e.g., “take-home identification cards will be instrumental in the field”). Three officers commented on the **workshop structure** (e.g., “huge fan of moving groups around for small blocks of instruction instead of leaving us all in the same room for hours”). Finally, five officers shared that the **workshop as a whole** was useful (e.g., “actually learning how to do my job better on my body of water”; “the well informed instruction by all the instructors”).

Survey respondents were also invited to provide suggestions on how the workshop could be improved. A total of 19 individuals chose to provide input. The most common suggestion was to have **more live specimens and a longer time period to handle the live specimens** (n=9), including a broader set of species and native species for comparison. Several officers (n=3) commented that a **quiz or practical** would be helpful to practice species ID and gain confidence. Others suggested **decreasing the amount of time spent on PowerPoint presentations** (n = 2). A few additional requests were to provide this training at the conservation police officer academy (n = 1), provide more examples of case reviews (n = 2), and provide large amounts of pocket-sized reference materials for dispersal in interactions with the general public (n = 1).

Workshop learning

We used several metrics to evaluate workshop effectiveness. First, levels of confidence were measured using the same approach as the pre-survey (see Table 8). Results indicated that average confidence in educating and providing instructions related to AIS had increased ($M = 3.86, SD = 0.73$) since the pre-survey ($M = 2.72, SD = 0.97$; see Figure 4).

Figure 4.

Changes in officer confidence in invasive species education before and after the workshop

Table 8.

Levels of confidence in providing education and instructions related to AIS

	M (SD)
Confidence¹ ($\alpha=.922, \Omega=.928, AVE=.811$)	3.86 (0.73)
Educating others about how to identify invasive species	3.84 (0.78)
Providing instructions to industry about how to follow laws pertaining to invasive species	3.82 (0.77)
Providing instructions to the general public about how to follow laws pertaining to invasive species	3.93 (0.78)

¹Measured on a Likert scale ranging from 1 (not at all confident) to 5 (Extremely confident)
Fit statistics: $\chi^2=150.845, df=80, \chi^2/df=1.89$; CFI=.925; TLI=.902; RMSEA=.102, SRMR=.073

Next, a suite of four learning indicators were examined (see Table 9). Drawing on past research (Rovai et al., 2009), we distinguished between cognitive learning, which focuses on knowledge recall, and psychomotor learning, which encompasses development of physical skills (e.g., species identification). We also examined individual learning, which represents individual engagement in the workshop, and situated learning, which represents how participants situate what was learned in a broader context (Andrade et al., 2023). All items demonstrated acceptable model fit and factor loading scores. **Respondents reported moderate to high levels of learning** (see Table 9), including cognitive ($M = 4.21, SD = 0.60$),

psychomotor ($M = 4.11$, $SD = 0.60$), individual ($M = 4.08$, $SD = 0.50$), and situated ($M = 4.05$, $SD = 0.51$).

Table 9.

Indicators of learning and engagement from the AIS workshop

Learning¹	M (SD)
<i>Cognitive</i> ($\alpha=.870$, $\Omega=.891$, $AVE=.736$)	4.21 (0.60)
I have learned a great deal in this workshop	4.21 (0.71)
My knowledge on aquatic invasive species has increased since the beginning of the workshop	4.26 (0.66)
I have seen clear changes in my understanding of aquatic invasive species	4.17 (0.64)
<i>Psychomotor</i> ($\alpha=.880$, $\Omega=.887$, $AVE=.725$)	4.11 (0.60)
I have expanded my physical skills as a result of this workshop	4.11 (0.70)
I will be able to use the physical skills from this workshop in my job	4.14 (0.68)
I can demonstrate to others the physical skills learned in this workshop	4.07 (0.66)
<i>Individual</i> ($\alpha=.730$, $\Omega=.713$, $AVE=.453$)	4.08 (0.50)
I actively participated in the workshop	4.18 (0.64)
I took the time to think about responses shared by others	4.12 (0.57)
I was comfortable volunteering my opinions to others	3.95 (0.66)
<i>Situated</i> ($\alpha=.810$, $\Omega=.810$, $AVE=.587$)	4.05 (0.51)
I took the time to review and think about the handouts	4.10 (0.51)
I compared topics discussed in the workshop with things I have learned elsewhere	4.08 (0.54)
I would like to participate in invasive species workshops in the future	3.98 (0.73)

¹Measured on a Likert scale where 1= “Strongly disagree” and 5= “Strongly agree”
Fit statistics: $\chi^2=150.845$, $df=80$, $\chi^2/df=1.89$; CFI=.925; TLI=.902; RMSEA=.102, SRMR=.073

Additional comments

Respondents had the opportunity to provide additional thoughts at the end of the questionnaire. Four provided comments:

- “Awesome presentation, great knowledge to know for the job”
- “Great workshop! Thank you for the good information”
- “Very good weekend, the best inservice I ever had”
- “Good program”

PUBLIC NEEDS ASSESSMENT

Methods

Data collection and sampling

We conducted an online survey of Illinois residents from October-November 2023 to complement the officer workshop. Respondents were recruited from a Qualtrics online panel and compensated for their participation. All respondents were at least 18 years old and lived in the U.S. state of Illinois. To take the survey, potential respondents had to have done at least one of the following three activities in Illinois in the past three years: 1) gone fishing; 2) participated in a recreational water activity (sailing, kayaking, canoeing, boating, jetskiing, etc.); and/or 3) kept aquatic plants, fish, or other animals in an aquarium or outdoor pond.

An online pilot test was conducted October 30-31, 2023 (n = 47). The results generated from this online pilot survey enabled us to tune the wording of survey questions and diagnose any potential methodological problems (e.g., completion rates, item interpretation). The final questionnaire is presented in Appendix D.

Following the pilot test, the survey was distributed to a larger panel of respondents via Qualtrics. Responses were discarded and replaced when respondents did not complete the entire survey, failed at least one of two “attention check” questions (Berinsky et al., 2014) or had response patterns that indicated extreme inattention or possible use of bots. This process continued until a final sample size of 783 was attained.

Data entry and analysis

All survey data were cleaned and analyzed by the research team following data collection. Descriptive statistics were estimated in SPSS version 28, while more advanced modeling took place in R Studio packages. All survey data were drawn from respondents who lived across the state of Illinois (see Figure 5).

Figure 5.
Zip codes represented by at least one survey respondent across the state of Illinois

Sampling bias assessment

Analyses were performed to test how well the data collected in this study represented the target populations of boaters, anglers, and aquarium hobbyists in Illinois. We compared our sample with previous research (van Riper et al., 2020; van Riper et al., 2019; Fitzgerald et al., 2021) that studied similar populations to identify bias that may have emerged from our sampling methods (see Table 10). Van Riper et al. (2020) conducted mail-back surveys with a sample of Illinois anglers who had purchased fishing licenses. Another study by van Riper et al. (2019) involved onsite surveys of water-users at the North Point Marina on Lake Michigan and Chain O'Lakes State Park. Finally, Fitzgerald et al. (2021) recruited aquarium and water garden hobbyists from Minnesota to their online survey via online hobbyist forums, social media, and in-store flyers.

In contrast to the sampling efforts by van Riper et al. (2020), van Riper et al. (2019) and Fitzgerald et al. (2021), the present study used an online panel provided by Qualtrics. This method resulted in a distribution of respondents that skewed younger ($\chi^2 = 126.091$, $p < .001$; $\chi^2 = 31.974$, $p < .001$; $\chi^2 = 80.130$, $p < .001$) and more female ($\chi^2 = 224.598$, $p < .001$; $\chi^2 = 44.629$, $p < .001$; $\chi^2 = 40.767$, $p < .001$) than the three examined past studies. The sample in this study that engaged in recreational angling also was less experienced in terms of both days fished ($t(1041) = 6.067$; $p < .001$) and years fished ($t(1041) = 17.943$; $p < .001$), as compared to the van Riper et al. (2020) study that sampled from license lists. These trends are typical for Qualtrics panels (Golebie et al., 2021, 2023) and have several implications for interpreting results. Women tend to report stronger environmental attitudes and greater engagement in pro-environmental behavior (Lynn & Longhi, 2011; Blankenberg & Alhusen, 2019), though younger anglers have reported lower awareness of AIS and lower likelihood of engaging in preventative behaviors (Nanayakkara et al., 2018; McEachran et al., 2022). Additionally, experience and skill are positively associated with knowledge of AIS and engagement in prevention measures (Golebie et al., 2023). Our results should be interpreted with these relationships in mind.

Table 10.

Comparison of current sample obtained via a Qualtrics panel with past research on anglers, boaters, and aquarium hobbyists using other sampling methods

	Current study by Golebie et al. (2024)	Mailback survey by van Riper et al. (2020)	On-site survey by van Riper et al. (2019)	Online survey by Fitzgerald et al. (2021)
<i>Sample frame</i>	Qualtrics panel	Fishing license lists	Park visitors	Social media; retail customers
<i>Audience</i>	Anglers, boaters, and aquarium hobbyists	Anglers	Boaters	Aquarium hobbyists
<i>Sample size</i>	N = 783	N = 260	N = 104	N = 479
<i>Age (M, SD)</i>	39.52, 14.75	54.33, 15.99	47.68, 13.84	--
18-29	26% (203)	9% (23)	14% (13)	15% (67)
30-49	48% (379)	27% (71)	33% (32)	35% (158)
50 or above	26% (201)	64% (165)	53% (51)	51% (230)
<i>Gender (% , N)</i>				
Male	40% (314)	94% (244)	76% (75)	54% (259)
Female	60% (467)	6% (16)	24% (24)	37% (177)
Other	0.3% (2)	0% (0)	--	3% (14)
<i>Race (% , N)</i>				
White	72% (563)	82% (221)	100% (95)	87% (327)
Black or African American	18% (140)	2% (6)	0% (0)	0.3% (1)
<i>Angling descriptives (M, SD)</i>				
Days fished in past year	14.64, 25.63	27.2, 37.13	--	--
Years of experience	16.54, 15.55	37.7, 19.00	--	--

Note. Some columns may not add up to 100%

Note. Some values are missing because of survey differences

Results from Public Needs Assessment

This section presents results using tables and figures, particularly frequency distributions for each variable included in the questionnaire. Data presented are typically valid percentages in each response category (i.e., percentages excluding missing values). Descriptive statistics, such as mean values and standard deviations are also included for appropriate variables. Per disciplinary standards within the environmental social sciences, Likert scale questions with five points or greater were treated as interval-level measures.

Descriptive information about survey respondents

Illinois residents were eligible to take the survey if, in the past three years, they had gone fishing, boating, or owned a home aquarium. Many respondents (56.4%) participated in at least two of these activities (see Table 11; Figure 6). Overall, 68% of respondents were anglers (n = 536), 65% were boaters (n = 512), and 41% were aquarium hobbyists (n = 323).

Figure 6. Proportion of respondents engaging in each activity

Table 11.

Activity participation by survey respondents

Activity type	N (%)
Anglers	536 (68.5)
Only participated in angling	151 (19.3)
Participated in angling and boating (and <u>not</u> aquarium hobby)	182 (23.2)
Participated in angling and aquarium hobby (and <u>not</u> boating)	56 (7.2)
Participated in angling, boating, and aquarium hobby	147 (18.8)
Boaters	512 (65.4)
Only participated in boating	127 (16.2)
Participated in angling and boating (and <u>not</u> aquarium hobby)	182 (23.2)
Participated in boating and aquarium hobby (and <u>not</u> angling)	56 (7.2)
Participated in angling, boating, and aquarium hobby	147 (18.8)
Aquarium hobbyists	323 (41.3)
Aquarium hobby only	64 (8.2)
Participated in angling and aquarium hobby (and <u>not</u> boating)	56 (7.2)
Participated in boating and aquarium hobby (and <u>not</u> angling)	56 (7.2)
Participated in angling, boating, and aquarium hobby	147 (18.8)

All respondents were asked whether they had purchased a fishing license between 2021-2023 (see Table 12). A majority of those who reported fishing in the past three years had purchased a license (74%). There are several reasons why individuals may not have purchased a license. For instance, children under 16 years old are exempt from license requirements, as are

disabled or blind residents, and residents on leave from active duty in the Armed Forces. Additionally, fishing licenses are not required for individuals fishing entirely on their own private property. It is, however, worth noting that the sizable proportion of non-licensed anglers would not be accounted for in traditional mailback surveys that are drawn from license lists. Additionally, we had 46 respondents (19%) who reported purchasing a fishing license while ultimately not deciding to fish, a population which also merits further study.

Table 12.

Individuals reporting having purchased a fishing license between 2021-2023

Fishing license purchase	Went fishing in past 3 years N (%)	Did not go fishing in past 3 years N (%)
Yes	394 (73.5)	46 (18.6)
No	142 (26.5)	201 (81.4%)

History of fishing participation

All respondents who indicated they had gone fishing the past three years (n = 536, 69%) were asked to provide information on their fishing experiences (see Table 13). Anglers fished primarily from the shoreline or dock (n = 295, 55%), or from both boats and shorelines (n = 32%), and reported an average of 16.54 years of experience with their activity (see Figure 7 and 8). Both days fishing and years of experience were right skewed (skewness = 7.386, 1.323).

Table 13.

Previous experiences and self-reported skill levels among recreational anglers

Previous experience	M (SD)
Total number of days fishing in 2022	14.64 (25.63)
Total number of years fishing ¹	16.54 (15.55)
Self-reported fishing skills in comparison to other anglers ²	2.95 (1.06)
Primary location of fishing activities N (%)	
Fishing from the shoreline or dock (including wading)	295 (55.0)
Fishing from a boat	71 (13.2)
I spend about an equal amount of time fishing from boats and shorelines	170 (31.7)

¹Estimate included fishing activities in 2023

²Measured on a Likert scale ranging from 1 (Much lower than average) to 5 (Much higher than average)

Figure 7.

Years of angling experience reported by Illinois residents who had fished at least once between 2021-2023

Figure 8.

Number of days angling in 2022 reported by Illinois residents. Three outliers (365, 200, and 120 days) were removed for this visualization

Anglers were also asked to report the species they commonly target (see Table 14). Catfish were the most common target species, with over half of anglers indicating they frequently fish for this species (n = 322, 60%). Other common target species included bluegill (n = 237, 44%), largemouth bass (n = 181, 34%), lake trout (n = 178, 33%), and crappie (n = 169, 32%).

Table 14.

All species targeted by anglers

Species	N (%)
Atlantic salmon	68 (12.7)
Bluegill	237 (44.2)
Brook trout	43 (8.0)
Brown trout	56 (10.4)
Carp	131 (24.4)
Catfish	322 (60.1)
Chinook / king salmon	24 (4.5)
Coho salmon	30 (5.6)
Crappie	169 (31.5)
Drum / sheepshead	20 (3.7)
Gar	16 (3.0)
Lake trout	178 (33.2)
Largemouth bass	181 (33.8)
Muskie	38 (7.1)
Northern pike	62 (11.6)
Rainbow trout / steelhead	50 (9.3)
Smallmouth bass	147 (27.4)
Walleye	101 (18.8)
White bass	92 (17.2)
Whitefish	80 (14.9)
Yellow perch	79 (14.7)
Other	19 (3.5)

Note. Column totals may not equal 100% because respondents were asked to check all that applied

Anglers who selected 'other' indicated they had no particular target species (n = 12), fished for striped bass (n = 1), any bass (n = 2), smelt (n=1), or beta fish (n = 1), or did not elaborate on why they chose 'other' (n = 2).

Given that live bait can be a vector for species introductions, we asked how often anglers used live bait (see Table 15). A majority of anglers (96%) reported using live bait at least occasionally.

Table 15.*Frequency of live bait use among respondents who reported fishing (n = 536)*

Bait use¹	N (%)
Frequency of live bait use [M, SD]	[3.42, 1.14]
Never	23 (4.3)
Occasionally	113 (21.1)
About half the time I go fishing	113 (21.1)
Most of the time	189 (35.3)
Every time I go fishing	98 (18.3)

¹Measured on a 5-point Likert scale ranging from 1 (Never) to 5 (Every time I go fishing)**History of boating participation**

Boaters reported an average of 11.69 years of boating experience (see Table 16). The average number of days boating in the past year was 13.56, but with a high degree of variation among respondents ($SD = 22.72$). Both days boating and years of experience were right skewed (skewness = 8.496, 1.722; see Figures 9 and 10). Just over half (59%) borrowed, rather than owned, the watercraft they used.

Table 16.*Previous experiences and self-reported skill levels among recreational water users*

Previous experience	M (SD)
Total number of days boating in 2022	13.56 (22.72)
Total number of years boating ¹	11.69 (12.41)
Boating skills in comparison to other boaters ²	3.09 (0.97)
Type of boat used most often N (%)	
My own boat that I trailer between sites	112 (22.0)
My own boat that I keep docked or moored at one location for a season	95 (18.6)
A boat I do not own, such as a rental, or a boat I borrow from friends or family	303 (59.4)

¹Estimate included boating activities in 2023²Measured on a Likert scale ranging from 1 (Much lower than average) to 5 (Much higher than average)

Figure 9.

Years of boating experience reported by Illinois residents who had gone boating at least once between 2021-2023

Figure 10.

Number of days boating in 2022 reported by Illinois residents. Two outliers (365 days and 150 days) were removed for this visualization

We asked respondents about their recreational activities (see Table 17), including which aquatic recreation they engaged in most frequently (see Table 18). The most common activity was boating: 72% of respondents had gone boating at least once and 47% reported it was their most frequent activity. Approximately 20% of respondents reported kayaking to be their most frequent activity, while 15% listed canoeing. A minority of respondents reporting sailing (6%), jetskiing (7%), or other types of activities (4%) to be their most common form of aquatic recreation.

Table 17.

Recreational activities reported by water users (n=512)

Recreation type	N (%)
Boating	370 (72.3)
Canoeing	224 (43.8)
Kayaking	222 (43.4)
Jetskiing	125 (24.4)
Sailing	119 (23.2)
Other ¹	19 (3.7)

Note. Respondents could check all that applied so column totals may not equal 100%.

¹Respondents who selected ‘other’ listed swimming (n=4), paddle boarding (n=1), wading (n=1), tubing (n=1), diving (n=1), fishing (n=2), or listed non-aquatic activities (e.g., hiking)

Table 18.

Most frequent recreational activities

Recreation type	N (%)
Boating	239 (46.7)
Kayaking	103 (20.1)
Canoeing	75 (14.6)
Sailing	28 (5.5)
Jetskiing	37 (7.2)
More than one activity	11 (2.1)
Other ¹	18 (3.5)

¹Respondents who selected ‘other’ listed swimming (n=5), wading (n=1), tubing (n=1), diving (n=1), fishing (n=2), listed non-aquatic activities (e.g., hiking, discgolfing), or indicated that they didn’t participate in any activity ‘frequently’ (n=2).

History of aquarium hobby participation

Hobbyists reported an average of 7.05 years of experience with their activity (see Table 19). Approximately three quarters (72%) owned one or two tanks. Both years of experience and number of tanks owned were right skewed (skewness = 2.908, 4.982; see Figures 11 and 12). The most common type of aquarium that respondents owned was a small fishbowl (51%), though a variety of aquarium types were represented including larger aquariums (47%), saltwater aquariums (15%), koi ponds (18%), and indoor aquatic pets (24%).

Table 19.

Previous experiences and self-reported skill levels among aquarium hobbyists (n=323)

Previous experience	M (SD)
Total number of years of aquarium experience ¹	7.05 (7.46)
Level of expertise in comparison to other aquarium hobbyists ²	3.32 (0.97)
Total number of aquarium tanks maintained	
0 tanks	6 (1.9)
1 tank	156 (48.3)
2 tanks	75 (23.2)
3 tanks	37 (11.5)
More than 3 tanks	49 (15.2)
Type of aquarium owned N (%) ³	
Fishbowl(s) or small freshwater aquarium(s) of 5 gallons or less	165 (51.1)
Large freshwater aquarium(s) of 5 gallons or more	153 (47.4)
Saltwater aquarium(s) of any size	49 (15.2)
Koi pond(s) or water garden(s)	58 (18.0)
Tank(s) with indoor aquatic pets (turtles, frogs, etc.)	77 (23.8)

¹Estimate included hobby activities in 2023

²Measured on a Likert scale ranging from 1 (Much lower than average) to 5 (Much higher than average)

³Column totals may not equal 100% because respondents were asked to check all that applied

Figure 11.

Years of aquarium experience reported by Illinois residents who had owned a home aquarium between 2021-2023

Figure 12.

Number of tanks owned by each respondent who had owned a home aquarium between 2021-2023

Several questions were asked to determine the source of the aquatic species owned by respondents (see Table 20, Figure 13). The most common sources of species were chain stores, from which 91% of hobbyists reported sometimes or often obtaining fish species, and local fish stores, from which 82% of hobbyists reported sometimes or often obtaining their fish species.

Table 20.

Aquarium hobbyist frequency of purchasing aquatic species from various sources

Source of species	Never M (SD)	Sometimes M (SD)	Often M (SD)
Buy aquatic species from a chain store (PetCo, PetSmart, etc.)	28 (8.7)	162 (50.2)	133 (41.2)
Buy aquatic species from a local fish store	58 (18.0)	152 (47.1)	113 (35.0)
Buy aquatic species from a reputable breeder	131 (40.6)	116 (35.9)	76 (23.5)
Buy aquatic species over the internet	149 (46.1)	110 (34.1)	64 (19.8)
Personally collect species that I find in aquatic environments	162 (50.2)	89 (27.6)	72 (22.3)
Find fish species through a local classified system	172 (53.3)	94 (29.1)	57 (17.6)
Buy aquatic species through fish club events or meetings	182 (56.3)	88 (27.2)	53 (16.4)
Accept aquatic species from another hobbyist	161 (49.8)	10 (33.4)	54 (16.7)

Figure 13.

Aquarium hobbyist frequency of purchasing aquatic species from various sources

Familiarity with AIS

Respondents were asked to report their level of familiarity with ecological, behavioral, and legal aspects of AIS (see Table 21), to align with sources of knowledge assessed in past work (van Riper et al. 2020). This approach to measuring familiarity was reliable given high internal consistency that was measured using a “Cronbach’s alpha coefficient” that ranged from 0 – 1. Values above 0.6 were deemed acceptable in this study, and this applied to the questions that indicated familiarity with ecology ($\alpha=.875$), human behavior ($\alpha=.915$), and laws ($\alpha=.920$) related to AIS. We also confirmed that the relationships among these groupings of survey questions were more closely related with one another than with the broader types of familiarity we were trying to understand by estimating factor loading scores.

Table 21.

Familiarity with topics related to AIS

Familiarity¹	M (SD)
<i>Ecology ($\alpha=.875, \Omega=.875, AVE=.701$)</i>	<i>2.94 (1.11)</i>
The biological characteristics that make a species “invasive”	3.03 (1.21)
Names of species that are considered invasive	2.69 (1.25)
Ways that invasive species affect the environment	3.09 (1.27)
<i>Human behavior ($\alpha=.915, \Omega=.915, AVE=.782$)</i>	<i>2.84 (1.27)</i>
How you could be at risk of spreading invasive species	2.93 (1.38)
Types of actions you can take to prevent invasive species from spreading	2.82 (1.36)
How to complete recommended preventative actions	2.77 (1.37)
<i>Laws ($\alpha=.920, \Omega=.922, AVE=.797$)</i>	<i>2.65 (1.31)</i>
Laws restricting the spread of invasive species in Illinois	2.68 (1.43)
Penalties that may be incurred by violating Illinois laws related to invasive species	2.56 (1.42)
Agencies that are responsible for enforcing invasive species laws in Illinois	2.71 (1.38)

¹Measured on a 5-point scale ranging from 1 (Not at all familiar) to 5 (Extremely familiar)
Fit statistics: $\chi^2=181.983$, $df=24$, $p<.001$; CFI=.976; TLI=.964; RMSEA=.092, SRMR=.024

On average, **respondents were slightly to moderately familiar** with ecological facets of AIS ($M = 2.94, SD = 1.11$), human behavioral responses to AIS management ($M = 2.84, SD = 1.27$), and AIS laws ($M = 2.65, SD = 1.31$). We also asked how personally involved respondents were with the issue of AIS, meaning how relevant they feel the topic is to their own lives. Items were drawn from past research (Quick & Stephenson, 2007). **Respondents were moderately involved with the issue of AIS** ($M = 3.16, SD = 0.95$, see Table 22).

Table 22.*Levels of involvement in the issue of AIS*

Involvement¹	M (SD)
<i>Involvement ($\alpha = .873, \Omega = .877, AVE = .645$)</i>	3.16 (0.95)
The spread of aquatic invasive species is a personally relevant topic for me	3.43 (1.02)
I think about aquatic invasive species a great deal	3.06 (1.13)
I find myself bringing up aquatic invasive species in casual conversation	2.76 (1.25)
When aquatic invasive species come up in conversation I “tune in”	3.39 (1.08)

¹Measured on a Likert scale ranging from 1 (Strongly disagree) to 5 (Strongly agree)
 Fit statistics: $\chi^2=56.593$, $df=2$, $p<.001$; CFI=.966; TLI=.899; RMSEA=.187, SRMR=.028

Approximately **half (49%) of respondents had previously interacted with a conservation police officer** (see Table 23). These respondents included 27% who had interacted with a conservation police officer one or two times, and 23% who had three or more previous interactions. The remaining 51% of respondents had never interacted with a conservation police officer. Respondents also reported high levels of trust; just over half (54%) indicated they had high or very high levels of trust in conservation police officers. There was no significant relationship between number of past experiences with conservation police officers and general level of trust (person’s correlation = .036, $p=.315$).

Table 23.*Past interactions with conservation police officers*

Interactions	N (%)
Number of times interacting with a conservation police officer [M, SD]	[1.63, 3.15]
Zero	396 (50.6)
One	89 (11.4)
Two	118 (15.1)
Three	67 (8.6)
Four	34 (4.3)
Five or more	79 (10.1)
Level of trust in conservation police officers [M, SD] ¹	[3.62, 1.01]
None at all	28 (3.6)
Low	50 (6.4)
Moderate	286 (36.5)
High	250 (31.9)
Very high	169 (21.6)

¹Measured on a 5-point Likert scale ranging from 1 (None at all) to 5 (Very high), *in response to the question, “In general, how much trust do you have in conservation police officers?”*

Socio-demographic characteristics

Survey respondents were mostly White (72%), with an average age of 39.52 ($SD = 14.75$) (see Table 24). A total of 60% of respondents were women. Educational experiences varied; 38% had earned a high school diploma, another 22% held a bachelor's degree, and an additional 15% a graduate degree. Nearly two thirds (62%) reported an annual household income less than \$75,000 before taxes.

Table 24.

Socio-demographic profile of Illinois residents included in this research

Variables	N (%)
<i>Age [M, SD]</i>	[39.52, 14.75]
<i>Gender</i>	
Male	314 (40.1)
Female	467 (59.6)
Other	2 (0.3)
<i>Education</i>	
Some high school	21 (2.7)
High school graduate or GED	301 (38.4)
Associate's degree	170 (21.7)
Bachelor's degree	174 (22.2)
Graduate degree (MA, MS, PhD, JD, MD, etc.)	117 (14.9)
<i>Income</i>	
Less than \$24,999	94 (12.0)
\$25,000 to \$49,999	217 (27.7)
\$50,000 to \$74,999	172 (22.0)
\$75,000 to \$99,999	100 (12.8)
\$100,000 to \$149,999	104 (13.2)
\$150,000 and over	75 (9.6)
Prefer not to answer	21 (2.7)
<i>Race & Ethnicity¹</i>	
American Indian	11 (1.4)
Asian	30 (3.8)
Black or African American	140 (17.9)
Hispanic or Latino	100 (12.8)
Native Hawaiian or other Pacific Islander	4 (0.5)
White	563 (71.9)
Other	7 (0.9)

¹Respondents could check all that applied so column totals may not equal 100%.

Factors contributing to AIS-prevention behaviors

We developed several series of questions to measure the behavioral intentions of survey respondents to comply with laws related to AIS. The following laws were considered:

- No person may place or operate a vehicle, seaplane, watercraft, or other object of any kind in waters of this State if it has any aquatic plants or aquatic animals attached to the exterior of the vehicle, seaplane, watercraft, or other object. (625 ILCS 45/5-23)
- It shall be unlawful to remove natural water from waters of the State via bait bucket, livewell, baitwell, bilge, etc., or any other method. (Ill. Admin. Code tit. 17 § 875.50)
- It shall be unlawful to release any aquatic life into the wild in this State without first securing permission of the Department to do so, except that the owner of a body of water may release aquatic life indigenous to the State of Illinois into waters wholly upon his or her property. (515 ILCS 5/10-100)
- Only species on the list of approved species may be purchased without approval from the DNR.

Based on these laws, questions were developed for anglers, boaters, and hobbyists (see Table 25). For anglers, we considered behaviors related to cleaning fishing equipment, and behaviors related to proper bait use and disposal. Respondents were only presented with the actions related to the activity(s) they had indicated participating in at the start of the survey. We asked survey respondents how likely they were to engage in these behaviors over the next 12 months. Likelihood of engaging in preventative behaviors were moderate across all four behaviors considered; the mean ranged from 3.32 to 3.55 on a 5-point scale.

Table 25.

Intended behavior reported by Illinois residents across three types of activities

Intended Behavior¹	M (SD)
Angler behavior: Fishing equipment²	3.55 (1.06)
Conduct visual inspections of fishing equipment for invasive species when leaving a fishing site	3.16 (1.32)
Remove any visible plants and animals from fishing equipment before departing a fishing site	3.64 (1.33)
Dump water from buckets before leaving a fishing site	3.84 (1.29)
Angler behavior: Bait use²	3.32 (0.73)
Consult resources to verify whether a live bait species is invasive	3.00 (1.42)
Use an invasive bait species if it increases the amount and quality of fish you catch*	2.32 (1.45)
Release unused live bait into an environment it did not come from*	2.32 (1.46)
Report another angler who you know to be using prohibited invasive species as bait	2.92 (1.54)

Intended Behavior¹	M (SD)
<i>Boater behavior³</i>	3.42 (1.17)
Conduct visual inspections of watercraft for invasive species when leaving a waterway	3.06 (1.42)
Remove any visible plants and animals from watercraft and trailers before departing a launch site	3.51 (1.37)
Drain water from watercraft, buckets, bilge, and any other areas before leaving a waterbody	3.70 (1.30)
<i>Hobbyist behavior⁴</i>	3.49 (0.71)
Consult resources to verify whether an aquarium species is invasive	3.28 (1.42)
Avoid purchasing aquatic invasive species	3.87 (1.33)
Release pets, plants, or other organisms into the wild*	2.41 (1.58)
Donate or rehome a plant or animal you can no longer care for	3.21 (1.57)

¹Measured on a 5-point Likert scale from 1 (never) to 5 (every time)

²Behaviors that anglers (n=536) intend to perform in the next 12 months

³Behaviors that boaters (n=512) intend to perform in the next 12 months

⁴Behaviors that aquarium hobbyists (n=323) intend to perform in the next 12 months

*Reverse coded item

After responding to these questions, survey respondents were presented with the following information:

“There are several steps you can take to minimize the risk of spreading aquatic invasive species. Guidelines related to different hobbies are below:

Anglers: When leaving a fishing site, conduct visual inspections of fishing equipment for invasive species, remove any plants and animals, and dump water from buckets. Avoid using invasive species as bait. Consult the Illinois Department of Natural Resources website if you are unsure whether a live bait species is invasive. Dispose of unused live bait in the trash rather than dumping it in the waterbody.

Boaters: When leaving a waterway, conduct visual inspections of watercraft for invasive species, remove any visible plants and animals from watercraft and trailers, and drain water from all parts of the watercraft including buckets and bilge.

Aquarium hobbyists: Prior to purchasing new species, consult the Illinois Department of Natural Resources website to ensure the species is not invasive or prohibited. If you no longer care for a pet, do not release it into the wild.”

The purpose of providing this information was twofold. First, it ensured respondents knew which behaviors to keep in mind when completing the remainder of the survey. Second, it allowed the questionnaire to provide useful education to respondents regarding what behaviors they should consider completing in the future.

Drivers of behavior

Decisions to engage in behaviors such as cleaning of fishing and boating equipment to prevent the spread of AIS can be influenced by a variety of factors. Past research (e.g., Estevez et al., 2015; Golebie et al., 2021; Kothe et al., 2019) has pointed to the importance of risk perceptions in motivating AIS prevention behavior. Drawing on Social Exchange Theory (Emerson, 1976; van Riper et al., 2016), we can understand trust and trustworthiness as potential precursors to risk, especially when trying to understand reactions to authority figures like conservation police officers. Additionally, emotion is a powerful basis for behavior change, and a particularly relevant consideration when considering risk, which is often associated with fear (Rogers, 1975). Therefore, this study sought to understand each of these variables among Illinois residents and understand their relevance in predicting compliance with AIS laws (see Figure 14).

Figure 14.

Relevant variables for predicting intentions to follow laws related to AIS. Arrows indicate causal relationships among these variables

The first key driver of behavior included in this study was trustworthiness of conservation police officers. Three facets of trustworthiness were examined, including ability (i.e., skills and competencies) ($\alpha=.905$); benevolence (i.e., beliefs that the individual wants to help) ($\alpha=.877$); and integrity (i.e., perceptions that the individuals' values and principles align with one's own) ($\alpha=.885$). Items were drawn from past research (van Riper et al., 2016; Mayer & Davis, 1999), and demonstrated acceptable model fit and factor loading scores. **Respondents reported moderate to high levels of trustworthiness** (see Table 26) and evaluated the three types of trust similarly. Perceived ability ($M = 3.81, SD = 0.95$), benevolence ($M = 3.51, SD = 1.02$), and integrity ($M = 3.65, SD = 0.97$) were all perceived to be similarly high.

Table 26.

Trustworthiness of conservation police officers

Trustworthiness¹	M (SD)
Ability ($\alpha=.905, \Omega=.906, AVE=.707$)	3.81 (.95)
I trust conservation police officers' knowledge of the invasive species laws in Illinois	3.84 (1.11)
I feel confident about conservation police officers' ability to help people follow invasive species laws	3.82 (1.06)
Conservation police officers are known to be successful at invasive species education and enforcement	3.71 (1.08)
I trust conservation police officers' knowledge of invasive species	3.90 (1.02)
Benevolence ($\alpha=.877, \Omega=.877, AVE=.703$)	3.51 (1.02)
Conservation police officers are concerned about my welfare	3.60 (1.14)
My needs and desires are very important to conservation police officers	3.44 (1.15)
Conservation police officers will go out of their way to help me	3.51 (1.14)
Integrity ($\alpha=.885, \Omega=.887, AVE=.724$)	3.65 (.97)
Conservation police officers have a strong sense of justice	3.64 (1.08)
Conservation police officers try hard to be fair in their dealings with others	3.64 (1.06)
Sound principles seem to guide conservation police officers' actions	3.67 (1.08)

¹Measured on a Likert scale where 1= "Strongly disagree" and 5= "Strongly agree"
Fit statistics: $\chi^2=131.761, df=32, p<.001$; CFI=.984.; TLI=.977; RMSEA=.063, SRMR=.022

Next, we evaluated trust in conservation police officers, defined as “the willingness of a party to be vulnerable to another party based on the expectation that another will perform a particular action important to the trustor, irrespective of the ability to monitor or control that other party” (Mayer et al. 1995, p. 712). Trust includes both trust in decisions ($\alpha = .933$) and trust in values ($\alpha = .908$). We found acceptable model fit and factor loading scores that exceeded minimum acceptable thresholds. Respondents reported moderate to high levels of trust in both decisions ($M = 3.83, SD = 1.02$) and values ($M = 3.74, SD = 0.87$; See Table 27).

Table 27.

Trust in conservation police officers

Trust	M (SD)
<i>Trust in decisions</i>¹ ($\alpha=.933, \Omega=.934, AVE=.824$)	3.83 (1.02)
Educating you and others about how to identify aquatic invasive species	3.79 (1.09)
Providing instructions about how to follow laws pertaining to aquatic invasive species	3.84 (1.08)
Enforcing laws pertaining to aquatic invasive species	3.85 (1.08)
<i>Trust in values</i>² ($\alpha=.908, \Omega=.908, AVE=.768$)	3.74 (0.87)
Conservation police officers share my same values	3.74 (0.93)
Conservation police officers’ views are similar to my own	3.72 (0.95)
Conservation police officers’ goals are consistent with my own	3.76 (0.96)

Fit statistics: $\chi^2=31.779, df=8, p<.001.$; CFI=.994; TLI=.989; RMSEA=.062, SRMR=.014

¹Measured on a 5-point Likert scale from 1 (I do not trust conservation police officers at all) to 5 (I trust conservation police officers completely)

²Measured on a 5-point Likert scale from 1 (strongly disagree) to 5 (strongly agree)

Next, we evaluated perception of the risks posed by AIS by implementing a scale that had been developed in previous research (Golebie et al., 2021, 2023). Three types of risk perceptions were examined, including susceptibility to risk (i.e., likelihood that impacts would be experienced) ($\alpha = .869$); personal (i.e., the level of threat posed to individuals) ($\alpha = .837$); and social (i.e., the level of threat posed to communities) ($\alpha = .850$). We found acceptable model fit and factor loading scores exceeding minimum acceptable thresholds.

Respondents reported moderate risk perceptions (see Table 28). Specifically, respondents slightly agreed that their local environment was susceptible to AIS ($M = 3.36, SD = 0.86$), and expected that impacts to themselves ($M = 3.22, SD = 0.95$) and their community ($M = 3.19, SD = 0.97$) would be moderate.

Table 28.*Perceived risks posed by AIS*

Risk perceptions	M (SD)
<i>Susceptibility</i>¹ ($\alpha=.869$, $\Omega=.870$, $AVE=.692$)	3.36 (0.86)
My local environment is at risk of invasive species spread	3.37 (0.96)
It is likely that invasive species will spread to my local environment	3.39 (0.98)
The chance of invasive species spreading to my local environment is strong	3.33 (0.98)
<i>Personal</i>² ($\alpha=.837$, $\Omega=.843$, $AVE=.645$)	3.22 (.95)
Your appreciation of the beauty of the landscape	3.28 (1.00)
Your own enjoyment of recreational activities	3.22 (1.11)
Your own access to the waterbody	3.15 (1.16)
<i>Social</i>² ($\alpha=.850$, $\Omega=.854$, $AVE=.661$)	3.19 (0.97)
The local economy	3.08 (1.14)
The community in the region	3.12 (1.11)
Recreational opportunities for future generations	3.36 (1.08)

Fit statistics: $\chi^2=99.747$, $df=24$, $p<.001$; CFI=.981.; TLI=.971; RMSEA=.063, SRMR=.026

¹Measured on a 5-point Likert scale from 1 (strongly disagree) to 5 (strongly agree)

²Measured on a 5-point Likert scale from 1 (no impacts) to 5 (very severe impacts)

Next, we examined two types of emotions: 1) hope, defined as a positive emotion with an expectation of a favorable development; and 2) fear, defined as a negative emotion that emerges as a response to a threat. The survey questions were drawn from the Positive and Negative Affect Scale (PANAS) established in past research (Watson & Clark, 1994). Results of a confirmatory factor analysis showed good model fit and reliability across the two scales that measured hope ($\alpha=.848$) and fear ($\alpha=.890$). Respondents expressed positive emotions towards conservation police officers (see Table 29). On average, respondents agreed that they feel hopeful when thinking about conservation police officers ($M = 3.56$, $SD = 0.86$) and disagreed that they would feel fearful ($M = 2.40$, $SD = 0.99$).

Table 29.*Emotions felt when thinking about conservation police officers*

Emotion	M (SD)
<i>Hope</i> ($\alpha=.848$, $\Omega=.849$, $AVE=.652$)	3.56 (0.86)
Encouraged	3.49 (1.01)
Optimistic	3.55 (0.98)
Hopeful	3.66 (0.96)

Emotion	M (SD)
Fear ($\alpha=.890, \Omega=.891, AVE=.671$)	2.40 (0.99)
Nervous	2.52 (1.15)
Insecure	2.35 (1.11)
Jittery	2.46 (1.15)
Frightened	2.25 (1.17)

Fit statistics: $\chi^2=20.878, df=13, p=.075.$; CFI=.997; TLI=.995; RMSEA=.028, SRMR=.017

Note. Measured on a Likert scale where 1= “Strongly disagree” and 5= “Strongly agree”
One item (“curious”) was dropped from the hope scale due to factor loading <.40.

Though not part of our conceptual model, we also measured **self-efficacy** (i.e., beliefs that one has the ability to take a particular action) and **response-efficacy** (i.e., beliefs that a recommended action will effectively achieve a particular goal). These questions were adapted from past work (Bandura, 1977; Landon et al., 2018), and refined through previous research (Golebie et al., 2021, 2023). Both self-efficacy ($\alpha = .860$) and response-efficacy ($\alpha = .845$) were reliable and there was good model fit. Respondents reported high levels of self-efficacy ($M = 4.22, SD = 0.73$) and response efficacy ($M = 4.29, SD = 0.71$), indicating beliefs that they had the ability to take preventative actions, and that their actions would help prevent AIS spread (see Table 30).

Table 30.

Self-efficacy and response-efficacy related to behaviors that prevent the spread of AIS

Efficacy¹	M (SD)
Self-efficacy ($\alpha=.860, \Omega=.860, AVE=.673$)	4.22 (0.73)
I understand what I need to do in order to follow these guidelines and minimize the spread of invasive species	4.19 (0.82)
I am capable of performing the tasks required to follow invasive species prevention guidelines	4.26 (0.81)
I feel confident in my ability to follow the guidelines necessary to prevent aquatic invasive species from spreading	4.21 (0.85)
Response-efficacy ($\alpha=.845, \Omega=.845, AVE=.646$)	4.29 (0.71)
These guidelines help to prevent invasive species from spreading	4.28 (0.84)
My own actions to follow these guidelines will protect the local environment from invasive species	4.23 (0.81)
If everyone followed these guidelines, we could significantly lower the risk of spreading invasive species	4.37 (0.79)

Fit statistics: $\chi^2=28.490, df=8, p<.001.$; CFI=.993; TLI=.987; RMSEA=.057, SRMR=.013

Note. Measured on a Likert scale where 1= “Strongly disagree” and 5= “Strongly agree”

Relationships among drivers of behavior

This study used structural equation modeling techniques to understand relationships among hypothesized drivers of behavior including trustworthiness, trust, emotions, risk perceptions, and behavior (see Figure 15). The model shows these relationships with arrows indicating how one variable positively predicts another. Starting on the left-hand side of the model, **trustworthiness positively predicted trust** ($\beta = 0.80$). That is, the more individuals perceive conservation police officers had high levels of ability, benevolence, and integrity, the more they trusted in the decisions made, and values held by conservation police officers. Next, **trust in conservation police officers was associated with emotions people experienced when thinking about conservation police officers**. Specifically, trust positively predicted hope in conservation police officers ($\beta = 0.68$) and negatively predicted fear of conservation police officers ($\beta = -.13$). **Emotions, in turn, affected risk perceptions**. Hope in conservation police officers was positively associated with increased perceived threat of AIS ($\beta = 0.32$) and susceptibility to that threat ($\beta = 0.31$). Likewise, fear of conservation police officers positively predicted both perceived severity ($\beta = 0.22$) and susceptibility ($\beta = 0.19$).

Figure 15.

Drivers of compliance with AIS laws among boaters and anglers in Illinois. Fit statistics are $\chi^2=1638.473$, $df = 643$; $\chi^2/df=2.548$; $CFI = .951$, $TLI = .946$, $RMSEA = .044$, $SRMR = .055$. Black lines indicate positive relationships and red lines indicate negative relationships. Non-significant relationships are shown in grey dotted lines

We examined the direct influences of risk perceptions (i.e., severity and susceptibility) as well as emotions (i.e., hope and fear) on boating and angling actions related to AIS prevention. Relationships between risk and behavior were similar for both types of risk and both behaviors. Specifically, both **perceived severity of and susceptibility to species invasions positively influenced boating and angling behaviors**. The more susceptible someone feels to species invasions, and the more severe they perceive potential impacts to be, the more likely they are to comply with laws related to AIS. Risk perceptions can be activated by conveying the ways that AIS threaten entities that individuals care about. For instance, providing an example of how species threaten sportfishing opportunities is likely to resonate with anglers and result in greater concern about AIS, and ultimately greater likelihood of complying with relevant laws.

Behavior was also positively influenced by hope in conservation police officers. However, boating behaviors were negatively influenced by fear of conservation police officers. That is, the more people indicated they felt fearful of conservation police officers, the less likely they were to comply with laws designed to minimize species invasions via boats. The fear-behavior relationship was non-significant for angling behaviors. This difference may be related to the differences in enforcement outcomes for boaters versus anglers. Violating angling regulations can result in loss of fishing license, whereas violating boating regulations results in fines. The relatively less strict regulations for boaters could be contributing to the lack of engagement in compliance particularly when relationships with officers are perceived to be negative.

It is typically difficult to directly influence the emotions someone may feel when interacting with conservation police officers. Our results indicate that officers can indirectly influence emotions via trust. That is, the link between trust and emotion shows promise for promoting positive relationships between conservation police officers and the public. **By continuing to engage in practices that build trust, officers can continue fostering positive relationships.** For instance, responding to questions and requests from the public can help build perceived benevolence of officers. Similarly, striving for consistency in enforcement actions can foster perceived integrity. Ultimately, promoting trust can build the capacity of recreation management agencies.

Open-ended comments on survey

At the end of the questionnaire, respondents were invited to optionally provide any reactions they had to the study. The majority of respondents left the comment box blank (n=534, 68%), indicated they had no further comments (n = 100, 13%), or left brief positive comments, such as “very good study” or “thank you” (n = 101, 13%). A selection of the more substantive comments (n = 48) is below.

Twenty-four respondents indicated that taking the survey helped them learn about AIS:

- I love how this survey actually helped me understand the risks that invasive species cause and if I’m aware of them. They gave me ideas to take action too.
- I learned from the guidelines and feel they should be shared in various forms. The more knowledge we have the better the chances people will act accordingly.

Five respondents indicated the need for additional information and education regarding AIS:

- I love this as an educational tool. So many "weekend" hobbyists just don't get it!!
- I am going to research this, so I can do my part when I'm participating in the aqua areas of recreational activities and to be able to share this information with others I know.
- I don't recall seeing any booklets or brochures about invasive species. I always pick up the state's guidebooks to learn more about rules, etc. I would definitely do more about protecting against invasive species if I knew how to identify them.

Six respondents shared personal concerns about AIS:

- i live in romeoville and we use to have the electric current in the des plaines to fry the asian carps idk why they stopped
- love game wardens, we have been effected in my area with asian carp, its so bad ty for doing this study

Three individuals shared additional details about their recreational experience

- I used to go fishing every other week. Last few years it has been every couple of months. Success has been very poor in catching any thing.

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Aquatic Invasive Species in Illinois

We are developing a workshop to support conservation police officers in their work regarding aquatic invasive species. This workshop will be included in the February 2024 in-service training. You are being asked to participate in a survey to help inform workshop content. University of Illinois researchers will be evaluating the effectiveness of this workshop and using research findings to improve future workshops as well as invasive species prevention across the state. This survey takes 10 minutes to complete and you will not experience risks outside of those encountered in daily life. You must be 18 years or older and be physically present in the United States to participate. You have the option to not participate.

Check the following boxes to indicate your consent to participate in the study.

- I have read and understand the above information
- I certify that I am 18 years old or older.
- I certify that I am physically present in the United States.
- By clicking the “Submit” button to enter the survey, I indicate my willingness to voluntarily take part in this study.

Section 1 of 3: Aquatic invasive species

The first section of this survey is about your experiences with aquatic invasive species. We will use this information to better prepare for the workshop we will be providing during the February 2024 in-service training. We define aquatic invasive species as aquatic plants or animals that are introduced to an area where they are not native, establish abundant populations in the wild, and are difficult to control or eradicate.

1. How often do you encounter aquatic invasive species while working?

- Never Once a year or less A few times a year Around once a month At least once a week

2. What challenges have you experienced that have affected enforcement of aquatic invasive species laws?

3. There are several topics that may be covered during our workshop. How useful would it be for you to be trained in the following topics?

	Not at all useful	Slightly useful	Somewhat useful	Moderately useful	Extremely useful
a. Reviewing the causes and effects of invasive species spread	<input type="radio"/>				
b. Identifying invasive crayfish species	<input type="radio"/>				
c. Identifying invasive plant species	<input type="radio"/>				
d. Identifying invasive fish species	<input type="radio"/>				
e. Enforcing invasive species laws related to boating and angling	<input type="radio"/>				
f. Enforcing invasive species laws related to aquariums	<input type="radio"/>				

4. Please share any additional topics related to invasive species identification and enforcement that would be helpful for you to know.

5. Please report how confident you feel with the following activities related to aquatic invasive species.	Not at all confident	Slightly confident	Somewhat confident	Moderately confident	Extremely confident
a. Educating others about how to identify aquatic invasive species	<input type="radio"/>				
b. Providing instructions to industry about how to follow laws pertaining to aquatic invasive species	<input type="radio"/>				
c. Providing instructions to the general public about how to follow laws pertaining to aquatic invasive species	<input type="radio"/>				

Section 2 of 3: Information sources and resource preferences

In this section, we ask about the sources of information that you use most often. We will use your responses to identify resources that would be most helpful to distribute at the workshop.

6. We are interested in the sources of information that you rely on the most. In the past 12 months, how often have you consulted the following sources for information about aquatic invasive species while working?	Never	Rarely	Sometimes	Often	Very often
a. Other conservation police officers	<input type="radio"/>				
b. Biologists	<input type="radio"/>				
c. Online resources	<input type="radio"/>				
d. Species identification cards	<input type="radio"/>				
e. Brochures, fact sheets, or other printed material	<input type="radio"/>				
f. Other _____	<input type="radio"/>				

7. We are interested in the sources of information that you provide to others. How often do you direct members of the public to the following sources for information about aquatic invasive species?	Never	Rarely	Sometimes	Often	Very often
a. Other conservation police officers	<input type="radio"/>				

- | | | | | | |
|--|-----------------------|-----------------------|-----------------------|-----------------------|-----------------------|
| b. Biologists | <input type="radio"/> |
| c. Online resources | <input type="radio"/> |
| d. Species identification cards | <input type="radio"/> |
| e. Brochures, fact sheets, or other printed material | <input type="radio"/> |
| f. Other _____ | <input type="radio"/> |

8. What additional resources would be helpful for you to identify invasive species while in the field?

Not at all helpful Slightly helpful Somewhat helpful Moderately helpful Extremely helpful

- | | | | | | |
|--|-----------------------|-----------------------|-----------------------|-----------------------|-----------------------|
| a. Laminated fact sheets | <input type="radio"/> |
| b. Species identification cards | <input type="radio"/> |
| c. Lists of expert contacts who could be consulted | <input type="radio"/> |

8b. Please list any other resources that could be provided to support species identification:

Section 3 of 3: About You

9. About how many years, including this one, have you been a Conservation Police Officer? _____ Years

10. In what year were you born? _____

11. In which DNR management zone do you work?

- Northwest Region 1
- Northeast Region 2
- East-Central Region 3
- West-Central Region 4
- South Region 5

Thanks for your help!

If you have any additional thoughts about this study, please share them here.

Elizabeth Golebie, Ph.D.
Department of Natural Resources and Environmental Sciences
University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign
Email: golebie2@illinois.edu

INVASIVE PLANTS

Accidental hitchhikers

- Individuals cannot not leave a water access area, get on a highway, or enter a new Illinois body of water with plants or animals on the exterior of watercraft or boat trailers
- It doesn't matter which species (only duckweed is exempt); moving any can be harmful

Ponds, aquariums, and greenhouses

- Injurious species are prohibited from being bought, sold, traded, or transported within the state of Illinois
- Common prohibited species are below:

Parrot feather
Myriophyllum aquaticum

Yellow flag iris
Iris pseudacorus

Flowering rush
Butomus umbellatus

Eurasian Arrowhead
Sagittaria sagittifolia

Water spinach
Ipomoea aquatica

Brazilian Waterweed
Egeria densa

CONTACTS AND RESOURCES

Invasive fish

Katie O'Reilly | keo@illinois.edu

Invasive plants

Greg Spyreas | spyreas@illinois.edu

Greg Hitzroth | hitzroth@illinois.edu

Invasive crayfish

Chris Taylor | cataylor@illinois.edu

Dusty Swedberg | swedberg@illinois.edu

Phone apps for species ID

Seek

iNaturalist

Recommended websites

transportzero.org

invasivespeciesinfo.gov

nas.er.usgs.gov

VAN RIPER RESEARCH GROUP

Valuing *nature*. Changing *behavior*.

Aquatic Invasive Species Identification Guide

Conservation Police Officer
Workshop
February 2024

NORTHERN SNAKEHEAD

Channa argus

- Long, **cylindrical body** with brown mottled coloration
- Somewhat **flattened head; large mouth and protruding jaw** with canine-like teeth
- **Single dorsal fin** running the length of the body
- **Long anal fin**

GRASS CARP

Ctenopharyngodon idella

- Large, **torpedo shape** with small eyes
- Large overlapping body **scales with dark edges**
- **Olive-brown back** fading to silvery-white belly
- **Lateral line dips** ~10° for the first 6-8 scales

BLACK CARP

Mylopharyngodon piceus

- Narrow head and **slightly pointed snout**
- **Darker coloration**, including dark fins
- **Lateral line stays relatively straight**

RED SWAMP CRAYFISH

Procambarus clarkii

- Large adults are **dark red**; smaller crayfish can be light brown and covered with black and white spots.

- The body and top of the claws are **covered with small bumps**.
- Lines or ridges on the back between the head and tail **join or touch** at the middle of the back.

MARBLED CRAYFISH

Procambarus virginalis

- **Marbled pattern** covering the back and claws
- Dark **horizontal stripe on each side** of the body
- **Narrow claws**
- **No or small side spines** on extension between the eyes

RUSTY CRAYFISH

Faxonius (or Orconectes) rusticus

- Usually **light tan to light green** with some body regions darker or lighter than others.
- Claws have **red or orange tips** and black bands.
- A **large, rust-colored spot is on each side of the body** just forward of the tail.

- Lines or ridges on the back between the head and tail **do not join or touch** at the middle of the back.

Aquatic Invasive Species in Illinois

Workshop Evaluation

The purpose of this research study is to improve aquatic invasive species prevention in Illinois by providing training resources to conservation police officers. We are doing this study because we want to understand what conservation police officers need to effectively conduct educational and enforcement activities related to aquatic invasive species.

We would like you to complete this online survey, which asks questions about the usefulness of today's workshop and how much you feel you have learned. There are no known risks associated with participating in this study. By participating in the study, you may benefit from improved resources and trainings offered in the future. Additionally, we hope to learn more about the invasive species training needs of conservation police officers and how to continue enhancing our workshops.

Your decision to participate in this survey is voluntary and confidential. We will have no record of which individuals chose to participate or not to participate. Project team members at the University of Illinois will have access to the anonymized data and will maintain confidentiality to the extent of laws and university policies.

If you have any questions or complaints or if you feel you have been harmed by this research please contact the project leader, Carena van Riper, Department of Natural Resources and Environmental Sciences, University of Illinois, at cvanripe@illinois.edu.

If you have any questions about your rights as a research subject, including concerns, complaints, or to offer input, you may call the Office for the Protection of Research Subjects (OPRS) at 217-333-2670 or e-mail OPRS at irb@illinois.edu.

It should take approximately 5-10 minutes to complete the questionnaire. Participation in this study is voluntary. You can choose not to take part. You can choose not to finish the questionnaire or omit any question you prefer not to answer without penalty or loss of benefits.

Thank you for your participation.

Please check the following boxes to indicate your consent to participate in the study.

- I have read and understand the above information
- I certify that I am 18 years old or older.
- I certify that I am physically present in the United States.
- By clicking the "Submit" button to enter the survey, I indicate my willingness to voluntarily take part in this study.

Section 1 of 2: Workshop evaluation

1. Several topics were covered during our workshop. How useful was the training provided on each of the following topics?

	Not at all useful	Slightly useful	Somewhat useful	Moderately useful	Extremely useful
a. Reviewing the causes and effects of invasive species spread	<input type="radio"/>				
b. Identifying invasive crayfish species	<input type="radio"/>				
c. Identifying invasive plant species	<input type="radio"/>				
d. Identifying invasive fish species	<input type="radio"/>				
e. Enforcing invasive species laws related to boating and angling	<input type="radio"/>				
f. Enforcing invasive species laws related to aquariums	<input type="radio"/>				

2. How useful were each of the following training methods?

	Not at all useful	Slightly useful	Somewhat useful	Moderately useful	Extremely useful
a. Powerpoint presentations from invasive species experts	<input type="radio"/>				
b. Hands-on identification exercises with live specimens	<input type="radio"/>				
c. Take-home resources (ID cards, info sheets, etc.) about invasive species identification and enforcement strategies	<input type="radio"/>				

3. What was most useful about today's workshop? What worked well that you would recommend continuing in future workshops?

4. What suggestions do you have for future trainings related to aquatic invasive species? If you could have changed something about this workshop what would it be?

Section 2 of 3: Workshop outcomes

5. Please report how confident you feel with the following activities related to aquatic invasive species.

	Not at all confident	Slightly confident	Somewhat confident	Moderately confident	Extremely confident
a. Educating others about how to identify aquatic invasive species	<input type="radio"/>				
b. Providing instructions to industry about how to follow laws pertaining to aquatic invasive species	<input type="radio"/>				
c. Providing instructions to the general public about how to follow laws pertaining to aquatic invasive species	<input type="radio"/>				

6. Please report how much you have learned in the workshop.

	Strongly disagree	Disagree	Neither Disagree nor Agree	Agree	Strongly agree
a. I have learned a great deal in this workshop	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
b. My knowledge on aquatic invasive species has increased since the beginning of the workshop.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
c. I can see clear changes in my understanding of aquatic invasive species.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
d. I have expanded my physical skills as a result of this workshop	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
e. I will be able to use the physical skills from this workshop in my job	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
f. I can demonstrate to others the physical skills learned in this workshop	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

7. We would like to understand the variety of ways you may have engaged with the workshop. To what extent do you disagree or agree with the following statements about your experiences?

	Strongly disagree	Disagree	Neither Disagree nor Agree	Agree	Strongly agree
a. I actively participated in the workshop	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
b. I took the time to think about responses shared by others	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
c. I was comfortable volunteering my opinions to others	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
d. I took the time to review and think about the handouts	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
e. I compared topics discussed in the workshop with things I have learned elsewhere	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
f. I would like to participate in invasive species workshops in the future	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Section 3 of 3: About You

8. About how many years, including this one, have you been a Conservation Police Officer? _____ Years

9. How often do you encounter aquatic invasive species while working?

- Never Once a year or less A few times a year Around once a month At least once a week

10. In what year were you born? _____

11. In which DNR management zone do you work?

- Northwest Region 1
- Northeast Region 2
- East-Central Region 3
- West-Central Region 4
- South Region 5

Thanks for your help!

If you have any additional thoughts about this study, please share them here.

Elizabeth Golebie, Ph.D.
Department of Natural Resources and Environmental Sciences
University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign
Email: golebie2@illinois.edu

Aquatic Invasive Species in Illinois

The purpose of this research study is to enhance educational outreach and law enforcement related to aquatic invasive species prevention in Illinois. We are doing this study because we want to understand public needs related to aquatic invasive species prevention.

You are being asked to participate in a study on Illinois' residents views of aquatic invasive species. We would like you to complete this online survey, which asks questions about your hobby experiences, familiarity with aquatic invasive species, experience with state laws regarding invasive species, perceptions of Illinois conservation police officers, and demographic information. There are no known risks associated with participating in this study. You may enjoy sharing your hobby experiences, and we hope to learn more about how conservation police officers can support individuals in minimizing the spread of aquatic invasive species. You will be also compensated by Qualtrics for your participation in this study. You will be able to see the compensation value on your dashboard before entering the survey.

Participation in this survey is anonymous. Those of us at the University of Illinois who may see your information will maintain confidentiality to the extent of laws and university policies. Personal identifiers will not be published or presented.

If you have any questions or complaints or if you feel you have been harmed by this research please contact the project leader, Carena van Riper, Department of Natural Resources and Environmental Sciences, University of Illinois, at cvanripe@illinois.edu.

If you have any questions about your rights as a research subject, including concerns, complaints, or to offer input, you may call the Office for the Protection of Research Subjects (OPRS) at 217-333-2670 or e-mail OPRS at irb@illinois.edu.

It should take approximately 15 minutes to complete the questionnaire. Participation in this study is voluntary. You can choose not to take part. You can choose not to finish the questionnaire or omit any question you prefer not to answer without penalty or loss of benefits.

Check the following boxes to indicate your consent to participate in the study.

- I have read and understand the above information
- I certify that I am 18 years old or older.
- I certify that I am physically present in the United States.
- By clicking the "Submit" button to enter the survey, I indicate my willingness to voluntarily take part in this study.

Participant must check all above boxes to proceed to the screening question.

 Participant must respond 'yes' to at least one item in the screening question below.

During the past three years, which of the following have you done in Illinois?

- Gone fishing
- Participated in a recreational water activity (sailing, kayaking, canoeing, boating, jetskiing, etc.)
- Kept aquatic plants, fish, or other animals in an aquarium or outdoor pond
- None of the above

 Participant must report an Illinois zip code to participate.

What is your zip code? _____

Section 1 of 4: Background Information

Angler version: only presented to those who selected "gone fishing" in the screening question

In this section, we ask you to provide information about your fishing experiences.

1. **About how many days did you go fishing in 2022?** _____ Days
2. **About how many years, including this one, have you been fishing?** _____ Years

3. **Where have you spent most of your time fishing?**

- Fishing from the shoreline or dock (including wading)
- Fishing from a boat
- I spend about an equal amount of time fishing from boats and shorelines

4. **Which species do you frequently fish for? (Please select all that apply)**

- | | | |
|--|--|--|
| <input type="checkbox"/> Atlantic salmon | <input type="checkbox"/> Bluegill | <input type="checkbox"/> Brook trout |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Brown trout | <input type="checkbox"/> Carp | <input type="checkbox"/> Catfish |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Chinook / king salmon | <input type="checkbox"/> Coho salmon | <input type="checkbox"/> Crappie |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Drum / sheepshead | <input type="checkbox"/> Gar | <input type="checkbox"/> Lake trout |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Largemouth bass | <input type="checkbox"/> Muskie | <input type="checkbox"/> Northern pike |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Rainbow trout / steelhead | <input type="checkbox"/> Smallmouth bass | <input type="checkbox"/> Walleye |
| <input type="checkbox"/> White bass | <input type="checkbox"/> Whitefish | <input type="checkbox"/> Yellow perch |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Other: _____ | | |

5. **How would you rate your fishing skills compared to other anglers?**

- | | | | | |
|--------------------------|--------------------------|--------------------------|--------------------------|--------------------------|
| <input type="checkbox"/> |
| Much lower than average | Lower than average | Average | Higher than average | Much higher than average |

In this section, we ask you to provide information about your recreational water experiences.

1. Which recreational activities have you participated in since 2021?

(select all that apply)

- Sailing
- Boating
- Other: _____
- Kayaking
- Jetskiing
- Canoeing

2. Which activity do you participate in most frequently?

- Sailing
- Boating
- More than one of these activities (explain): _____
- Kayaking
- Jetskiing
- Canoeing
- Other: _____

3. In 2022, about how many days did you participate in the activity you selected in the previous question? _____ Days

4. About how many years, including this one, have you been participating in this activity? _____ Years

5. How would you rate your level of expertise in this activity compared to other recreationists?

- Much lower than average
- Lower than average
- Average
- Higher than average
- Much higher than average

6. Please select the description of the boat you use most often.

- My own boat that I trailer between sites
- My own boat that I keep docked or moored at one location for a season
- A boat I do not own, such as a rental, or a boat I borrow from friends or family

In this section, we ask you to provide information about your aquarium hobby.

1. What type of aquarium(s) do you have?

- Fish bowl(s) or small freshwater aquarium(s) of 5 gallons or less
- Large freshwater aquarium(s) of 5 gallons or more
- Saltwater aquarium(s) of any size
- Koi pond(s) or water garden(s)
- Tank(s) with indoor aquatic pets (turtles, frogs, etc.)

2. How many years, including this one, have you maintained at least one type of aquarium? _____ Years

3. How many aquarium tanks do you maintain? _____ Tanks

4. How would you rate your level of expertise compared to other hobbyists?

- | | | | | |
|----------------------------|--------------------------|--------------------------|--------------------------|-----------------------------|
| <input type="checkbox"/> | <input type="checkbox"/> | <input type="checkbox"/> | <input type="checkbox"/> | <input type="checkbox"/> |
| Much lower
than average | Lower than
average | Average | Higher than
average | Much higher
than average |

5. How often do you obtain new aquatic species from each of the following sources?

	Never	Sometimes	Often
a. Buy aquatic species over the internet	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
b. Buy aquatic species from a chain store (PetCo, PetSmart, etc.)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
c. Buy aquatic species from a local fish store	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
d. Buy aquatic species through fish club events or meetings	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
e. Accept aquatic species from another hobbyist	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
f. Find fish species through a local classified system	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
g. Buy aquatic species from a reputable breeder	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
h. Personally collect species that I find in aquatic environments	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Section 2 of 4: Experiences with aquatic invasive species

In this section, we ask about your experiences with aquatic invasive species. Aquatic invasive species are aquatic plants or animals that are introduced to an area where they are not native, establish abundant populations, negatively impact the environment or human activity, and are difficult to control or eradicate.

7. We would like to understand your familiarity with aquatic invasive species. How familiar are you with the following types of information?	Not at all familiar	Slightly familiar	Somewhat familiar	Moderately familiar	Extremely familiar
a. The biological characteristics that make a species “invasive”	<input type="radio"/>				
b. Names of species that are considered invasive	<input type="radio"/>				
c. Ways that invasive species affect the environment	<input type="radio"/>				
d. How you could be at risk of spreading invasive species	<input type="radio"/>				
e. Types of actions you can take to prevent invasive species from spreading	<input type="radio"/>				
f. How to complete recommended preventative actions	<input type="radio"/>				
g. Laws restricting the spread of invasive species in Illinois	<input type="radio"/>				
h. Penalties that may be incurred by violating Illinois laws related to invasive species	<input type="radio"/>				
i. Agencies that are responsible for enforcing invasive species laws in Illinois	<input type="radio"/>				

8. How vulnerable do you think your local environment is to invasive species?	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly Agree
a. My local environment is at risk of invasive species spread.	<input type="radio"/>				
b. It is likely that invasive species will spread to my local environment.	<input type="radio"/>				
c. The chance of invasive species spreading to my local environment is strong.	<input type="radio"/>				

9. If invasive species spread to your local ecosystem, how severe would you expect the impacts to be? Please indicate the severity of potential harm to...	No impacts	Mild impacts	Moderate impacts	Severe impacts	Very severe impacts
a. Your appreciation of the beauty of the landscape	<input type="radio"/>				
b. Your own enjoyment of recreational activities	<input type="radio"/>				

c. Your own access to the waterbody	<input type="radio"/>				
d. The local economy	<input type="radio"/>				
e. The community in the region	<input type="radio"/>				
f. Recreational opportunities for future generations	<input type="radio"/>				

10. We would like to understand how important the issue of aquatic invasive species is to you. To what extent do you agree or disagree with the following statements?

	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly Agree
a. The spread of aquatic invasive species is a personally relevant topic for me	<input type="radio"/>				
b. I think about aquatic invasive species a great deal	<input type="radio"/>				
c. I find myself bringing up aquatic invasive species in casual conversation	<input type="radio"/>				
d. When aquatic invasive species come up in conversation, I “tune in”	<input type="radio"/>				

Angler version: only presented to those who selected “gone fishing” in the screening question

11a. Think about your fishing activities over the next 12 months. How frequently do you plan to engage in each of the following?

	Never	Occasionally	About half the time	Most of the time	Every time
a. Conduct visual inspections of fishing equipment for invasive species when leaving a fishing site	<input type="radio"/>				
b. Remove any visible plants and animals from fishing equipment before departing a fishing site	<input type="radio"/>				
c. Dump water from buckets before leaving a fishing site	<input type="radio"/>				

11aa. How frequently do you use live bait?

<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Never	Occasionally	About half the time I go fishing	Most of the time	Every time I go fishing

11ab. Think about your fishing activities over the next 12 months. How frequently do you plan to engage in each of the following?

	Never	Occasionally	About half the time	Most of the time	Every time
--	-------	--------------	---------------------	------------------	------------

a. Consult resources to verify whether a live bait species is invasive	<input type="radio"/>				
b. Use an invasive bait species if it increases the amount and quality of fish you catch	<input type="radio"/>				
c. Release unused live bait into an environment it did not come from	<input type="radio"/>				
d. Report another angler who you know to be using prohibited invasive species as bait	<input type="radio"/>				

Boaters version: Only presented to those who selected “participated in a recreational water activity” in the screening question

11b. Think about your boating activities <u>over the next 12 months</u>. How frequently do you plan to engage in each of the following?	Never	Occasionally	About half the time	Most of the time	Every time
a. Conduct visual inspections of watercraft for invasive species when leaving a waterway	<input type="radio"/>				
b. Remove any visible plants and animals from watercraft and trailers before departing a launch site	<input type="radio"/>				
c. Drain water from watercraft, buckets, bilge, and any other areas before leaving a waterbody	<input type="radio"/>				

Aquarium version: only presented to those who selected “kept aquatic fish, plants, or other animals” in the screening question

11c. Think about your aquarium hobby activities <u>over the next 12 months</u>. How frequently do you plan to engage in each of the following?	Never	Occasionally	About half the time	Most of the time	Every time
a. Consult resources to verify whether an aquarium species is invasive	<input type="radio"/>				
b. Avoid purchasing aquatic invasive species	<input type="radio"/>				
c. Release pets, plants, or other organisms into the wild	<input type="radio"/>				
d. Donate or rehome a plant or animal you can no longer care for	<input type="radio"/>				

All respondents proceed to the remainder of the questionnaire

There are several steps you can take to minimize the risk of spreading aquatic invasive species. Guidelines related to different hobbies are below:

Anglers: When leaving a fishing site, conduct visual inspections of fishing equipment for invasive species, remove any plants and animals, and dump water from buckets.

Avoid using invasive species as bait. Consult the Illinois Department of Natural Resources website if you are unsure whether a live bait species is invasive. Dispose of unused live bait in the trash rather than dumping it in the waterbody.

Boaters: When leaving a waterway, conduct visual inspections of watercraft for invasive species, remove any visible plants and animals from watercraft and trailers, and drain water from all parts of the watercraft including buckets and bilge.

Aquarium hobbyists: Prior to purchasing new species, consult the Illinois Department of Natural Resources website to ensure the species is not invasive or prohibited. If you no longer care for a pet, do not release it into the wild.

12. We would like to know how easy or difficult it may be to follow these guidelines. Please report your agreement or disagreement with the statements below.	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly Agree
a. I understand what I need to do in order to follow these guidelines and minimize the spread of invasive species.	<input type="radio"/>				
b. I am capable of performing the tasks required to follow invasive species prevention guidelines.	<input type="radio"/>				
c. I feel confident in my ability to follow guidelines necessary to prevent aquatic invasive species from spreading.	<input type="radio"/>				
d. These guidelines help to prevent invasive species from spreading.	<input type="radio"/>				
e. My own actions to follow these guidelines will protect the local environment from invasive species.	<input type="radio"/>				
f. If everyone followed these guidelines, we could significantly lower the risk of spreading invasive species.	<input type="radio"/>				

Section 3 of 4: Experiences with conservation police officers

13. How many times have you interacted with a conservation police officer?

_____ Times

14. Please report how comfortable you are allowing conservation police officers to make decisions about various aspects of aquatic invasive species.	I do not trust CPOs at all	I slightly trust CPOs	I moderately trust CPOs	I mostly trust CPOs	I trust CPOs completely
a. Educating you and others about how to identify aquatic invasive species	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
b. Providing instructions about how to follow laws pertaining to aquatic invasive species	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

c. Enforcing laws pertaining to aquatic invasive species	<input type="radio"/>				
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15. We would like to better understand the extent to which you think your values align with conservation police officers. Please report your agreement or disagreement with the statements below.

	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly Agree
a. Conservation police officers share my same values	<input type="radio"/>				
b. Conservation police officers' views are similar to my own	<input type="radio"/>				
c. Conservation police officers' goals are consistent with my own	<input type="radio"/>				

16. Please evaluate these statements about the trustworthiness of conservation police officers.

	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly Agree
a. I trust conservation police officers' knowledge of the invasive species laws in Illinois	<input type="radio"/>				
b. I feel confident about conservation police officers' ability to help people follow invasive species laws	<input type="radio"/>				
c. Conservation police officers are known to be successful at invasive species education and enforcement	<input type="radio"/>				
d. I trust conservation police officers' knowledge of invasive species	<input type="radio"/>				
e. Conservation police officers are concerned about my welfare	<input type="radio"/>				
f. My needs and desires are very important to conservation police officers	<input type="radio"/>				
g. Conservation police officers will go out of their way to help me	<input type="radio"/>				
h. Conservation police officers have a strong sense of justice	<input type="radio"/>				
i. Conservation police officers try hard to be fair in their dealings with others	<input type="radio"/>				
j. Sound principles seem to guide conservation police officers' actions	<input type="radio"/>				

17. In general, how much trust do you have in conservation police officers?

None
 Low
 Moderate
 High
 Very high

18. When thinking about conservation police officers, I feel...

	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly Agree
	<input type="radio"/>				

a. Nervous	<input type="radio"/>				
b. Encouraged	<input type="radio"/>				
c. Insecure	<input type="radio"/>				
d. Optimistic	<input type="radio"/>				
e. Hopeful	<input type="radio"/>				
f. Jittery	<input type="radio"/>				
g. Curious	<input type="radio"/>				
h. Frightened	<input type="radio"/>				

Section 4 of 4: About You

19. What is your gender? Male Female Other

20. In what year were you born? _____

21. What is your annual household income (in USD) before taxes?

- \$24,999 or lower
 \$25,000-\$49,999
 \$50,000-\$74,999
 \$75,000-\$99,999
 \$100,000-\$124,999
 \$125,000-\$149,999
 \$150,000-\$174,999
 \$175,000-\$199,999
 \$200,000 or higher
 Prefer not to answer

22. What is the highest level of education you have completed? (Please ✓ one)

- Some high school
 High school graduate or GED
 Associate's degree
 Bachelor's degree
 Graduate degree (MA, MS, PhD, JD, MD, etc.)

23. With which racial or ethnic group(s) do you identify? (Please ✓ all that apply)

- White
 Black or African American
 Asian
 Native Hawaiian or Pacific Islander
 American Indian or Alaska Native
 Hispanic or Latino
 Other: _____

24. Have you purchased a fishing license between 2021 and 2023?

- Yes No

Thanks for your help!

If you have any additional thoughts about this study, please share them here.

Elizabeth Golebie, Ph.D.
Department of Natural Resources and Environmental Sciences
University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign
Email: golebie2@illinois.edu